

1 **USING DIRECTED ACYCLIC GRAPHS TO ASSESS COLLIDER AND CONFOUNDING BIAS**
2 **IN REVIEWS OF OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES: AN ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE USING THE**
3 **IMPACT OF RESIDENTIAL EXPOSURE TO ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATIONS ON HUMAN**
4 **HEALTH**

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7

8 **ABSTRACT**

9 **Background**

10 Bias assessment in systematic reviews of observational studies commonly focuses on whether
11 key confounders were controlled, but rarely evaluates whether adjustment strategies may have
12 introduced bias through control of colliders or mediatorsBias assessment in systematic reviews
13 of observational studies relies on identifying variables that should be controlled as confounders.
14 However, there are no formal approaches to ensuring unnecessary control of colliders is
15 assessed in systematic reviews. In primary observational research, directed acyclic graphs
16 (DAGs) are used to explicitly represent hypothesized causal structures, identify variables
17 required to block non-causal (biasing) pathways, and distinguish confounders from variables
18 that should not be adjusted for. How DAG-based reasoning can be systematically incorporated
19 into bias assessment during evidence synthesis remains insufficiently explored.In primary
20 observational research, directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) help researchers visualize a
21 hypothesized causal framework for an exposure-outcome relationship and identify variables that
22 must be controlled to estimate the causal effect of the exposure on the outcome, and non-
23 confounding variables, which, if controlled, could introduce bias.

24 **Objective**

25 The primary objective of this study was to demonstrate how an existing, population-level DAG
26 can be used as a reference framework to assess potential confounding and adjustment-related
27 bias in a systematic review of observational studies. The secondary objective was to evaluate
28 whether primary studies reported a rationale for covariate selectionThe primary objective was to
29 evaluate whether incorporating a DAG into the bias assessment enabled the assessment of
30 open biasing pathways due to uncontrolled confounders or controlled collider variables. The
31 secondary objective was to determine if authors provided the rationale for the variables
32 controlled in the model and reported if the goal was to estimate the direct or total effect of the
33 exposure on the outcome.

34 **Methods**

35 We examined a subset of observational studies identified through a living systematic review
36 assessing community health effects associated with residential proximity to animal feeding
37 operations (AFOs). Studies were eligible if they sought to estimate a causal effect. For studies
38 examining lower respiratory outcomes, covariates reported by study authors were mapped onto
39 nodes in a previously published population-level DAG. The DAG was then used to assess
40 whether reported adjustment strategies were theoretically sufficient to block non-causal
41 pathways and whether adjustment for colliders or other inappropriate variables may have
42 occurred. We also reviewed each study for explicit justification of covariate selection. We
43 examined observational studies investigating a relationship between residential proximity to
44 AFOs and lower respiratory conditions in humans to identify studies that reported incident
45 events and therefore assessed a causal association. We aim to map the variables controlled by
46 the authors onto a DAG to identify any open biasing pathways. We also evaluated if authors
47 reported the rationale for the inclusion of variables selected for control.

48 **Results**

49 Among 36 studies identified in the parent review Of 36 studies investigating a relationship
50 between residential proximity to AFOs and lower respiratory conditions in humans, 17 reported
51 incident outcomes and met inclusion criteria. None of the included studies reported using a DAG
52 or an explicit causal framework to guide covariate selection. Eight studies examined lower
53 respiratory outcomes and could be evaluated using the reference DAG. In six of these studies,
54 adjustment for at least one variable identified as a collider in the reference DAG opened a non-
55 causal pathway between exposure and outcome. In the remaining two studies, it was unclear
56 whether potential confounding pathways, particularly those related to socioeconomic factors
57 were addressed through study design or population characteristics, precluding firm conclusions.
58 reported incident events and were eligible for the study. However, none of the observational
59 studies used a DAG to select their confounders or avoid control of colliders. We found 8 studies
60 that reported lower respiratory disease. For those 8 studies we used a previously published
61 DAG to assess if open biasing pathways remained after control for the variables reported by the
62 authors. In six of the eight studies, adjustment for a collider variable opened a biasing pathway.
63 For two of the eight studies, it was unclear if the hypothesized biasing pathways associated with
64 socioeconomic status were controlled by the study design and study population, and so no
65 conclusion was reached. No authors reported whether the goal was to estimate the total or
66 direct effect of exposure on the outcome.

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68 **Conclusions**

69 This study illustrates how DAG-based reasoning, using an existing population-level causal
70 diagram, can complement conventional risk-of-bias approaches in systematic reviews by
71 making assumptions about confounding and inappropriate adjustment explicit. Incorporating
72 DAGs into evidence synthesis may improve transparency in bias assessment and support more
73 interpretable causal reasoning in reviews of observational studies.

74 Systematic reviewers should consider incorporating a DAG into the approach for assessment of
75 bias in reviews of observational studies to ensure a comprehensive assessment of biasing
76 pathways.

77 **Keywords:** Directed Acyclic Graphs, agriculture, Causal Effect, Confounding, Observational
78 Studies

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93 **CRedit statement:**

94 **Brayan Alexander Fonseca Martinez:** Data curation, investigation, formal analysis, writing
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106 **INTRODUCTION**

107 Observational studies encompass a wide range of designs and purposes, including descriptive,
108 surveillance, and hypothesis-generating research. In many applied fields, however,
109 observational data are also commonly used to address questions that are causal in nature,
110 particularly when randomized controlled trials are infeasible, unethical, or impractical. In such
111 settings, researchers often seek to estimate the effect of an exposure on a health outcome
112 using observational designs, even if this causal objective is not always made explicit (Hernán,
113 2018).

114 When observational studies are interpreted as providing evidence about causal effects, the
115 distinction between causation and confounding becomes critical. Without explicit articulation of
116 the assumed causal structure underlying an exposure–outcome relationship, conventional
117 multivariable adjustment strategies may inadvertently introduce bias through incomplete control
118 of confounding or through inappropriate adjustment for variables such as mediators or colliders.
119 This challenge has been widely documented across applied epidemiologic research, where
120 traditional definitions of confounding and automated variable selection procedures can leave
121 investigators vulnerable to controlling the wrong types of variables (Correia et al., 2025; Parra et
122 al., 2021). **As a result, formal causal reasoning frameworks have been increasingly emphasized**
123 **as a means to improve transparency and validity in observational causal inference (Churilov et**
124 **al., 2025; Gail et al., 2019).** One of the key objectives of observational studies is to infer cause
125 and effect, making the disentanglement of causation from confounding a critical component.
126 Understanding the risk of bias in observational studies is critical to ensure inferences are
127 appropriate and that gaps in knowledge are identified and can be rectified.

128 Directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) are one such framework. In primary observational research,
129 DAGs are increasingly used to make explicit the hypothesized causal structure linking an
130 exposure and an outcome, thereby supporting the identification of variables that may require
131 control to estimate a causal effect, as well as variables that should not be controlled because
132 doing so could introduce bias (Tennant et al., 2021; Digiale et al., 2023). Importantly, the utility
133 of a DAG is contingent on some assumptions. First, the specified graph must reasonably reflect
134 the underlying data-generating mechanisms operating in the target population. Second,
135 conditioning on variables must occur only through explicit analytical decisions such as statistical
136 adjustment rather than implicitly through sample selection, restriction, or stratification. These
137 assumptions represent necessary preconditions for using DAGs to reason about confounding

Commented [Author2]: Parra.observational studies: a review of papers published in a general medical journal

Correia. Confounder selection in observational studies in high-impact medical and epidemiological journals

Commented [Author3]: Conducting descriptive epidemiology and causal inference studies using observational data: A 10-point primer for stroke researchers

Design choices for observational studies of the effect of exposure on disease incidence

138 and other sources of bias. (Digitale et al., 2022; Hernán and Robins, 2020; Sauer and
139 VanderWeele, 2013).

140 Our motivation for exploring how DAGs could help reviewers conduct a comprehensive bias
141 assessment stem from our experience with two previous systematic reviews on this topic, where
142 evaluating bias, particularly in relation to confounding, has been a central and especially
143 challenging aspect of the analysis. Usually confounding bias assessment is limited to “Did the
144 authors include the main confounders?”. an approach reflected in several risk-of-bias
145 frameworks, including ROBINS-E This is an approach proposed by the ROBINS-E group
146 (Higgins et al. 2024). However, such an approach does not account for the complex pathways
147 that might exist in causal questions, and therefore we were interested in different assessment
148 methods or tools. One approach to assessing risk of bias due to confounding in observational
149 studies is to evaluate which variables the investigators have controlled and whether these
150 include the major confounders. The challenge lies however not only in identifying and controlling
151 for true confounders, but also in avoiding the erroneous adjustment for other types of variables,
152 such as colliders and mediators, which can introduce bias rather than reduce it which can
153 introduce bias if mistakenly controlled (Digitale et al., 2023; Tennant et al., 2021). An additional
154 motivation for incorporating DAG-based reasoning into evidence synthesis is the central role of
155 systematic reviews in causal assessment. Causal inference in observational research should
156 not rely on single studies in isolation, even when those studies employ rigorous analytical
157 methods. Rather, causal interpretation emerges through the synthesis of evidence across
158 multiple studies, making transparent evaluation of assumptions, sources of bias, and analytic
159 choices essential at the review level.

160 DAGs offer a complementary approach. When used at the population level, DAGs encode
161 assumptions about how exposures, outcomes, confounders, mediators, colliders, and other
162 variables are causally related in the real world, independent of any specific study design or
163 measurement process (Williams et al., 2018; Bours, 2021). By explicitly representing
164 hypothesized causal and non-causal pathways, DAGs allow investigators and reviewers to
165 reason systematically about which variables should be controlled to block biasing (backdoor)
166 paths while preserving causal pathways of interest To avoid these pitfalls, directed acyclic
167 graphs (DAGs) are a key tool in observational research. DAGs when used as tools for
168 designing observational studies of causal questions, allow researchers to visualize causal
169 pathways and biasing pathways that impact effect size estimation. DAGs also help researchers
170 distinguish between confounders, mediators, and colliders, ensuring that only the necessary

171 variables—those that close non-causal biasing paths—are adjusted for (Bours, 2021; Williams
172 et al., 2018). As such DAGs are tools that can help researchers determine what variables
173 should be controlled to allow estimation of either the direct or total effect of an exposure of
174 interest on an outcome of interest.

175 A key concept underlying the use of DAGs is d-separation, which provides a formal criterion for
176 determining whether a set of variables blocks all non-causal pathways between an exposure
177 and an outcome (Pearl, 2009; Textor et al., 2016). Two variables are considered d-separated if
178 all paths connecting them are blocked through conditioning on an appropriate set of variables,
179 such that any remaining association can be interpreted as causal under the assumed DAG. In
180 applied epidemiologic research, d-separation allows investigators and reviewers to evaluate
181 whether reported covariate adjustment sets are theoretically sufficient to control confounding
182 while avoiding inappropriate adjustment for mediators or colliders that could induce bias (Cole et
183 al., 2010; Hernán & Robins, 2020).

184 In applied epidemiologic research, d-separation allows investigators and reviewers to evaluate
185 whether the covariates adjusted for in an analysis are theoretically sufficient to control
186 confounding, while also avoiding inappropriate adjustment for other types of variables that can
187 introduce bias (Tennant et al., 2021). Variables that lie on a common cause pathway of both the
188 exposure and the outcome act as confounders and must be adjusted for to block biasing paths.
189 In contrast, mediators lie on the causal pathway from exposure to outcome and should not be
190 adjusted for when estimating total effects, whereas colliders (variables caused by two or more
191 upstream variables) should generally not be conditioned on, as doing so can open otherwise
192 closed biasing pathways (Cole et al., 2010; Hernán & Robins, 2020).

193 In the context of evidence synthesis, this framework provides a principled way to assess
194 whether study-specific adjustment strategies are capable, *in theory*, of closing biasing
195 pathways, independent of statistical significance or effect magnitude. This perspective is
196 particularly relevant for systematic and scoping reviews of observational studies, where
197 determining whether confounding has been adequately addressed requires explicit
198 consideration of causal assumptions rather than reliance on variable lists or model-building
199 heuristics alone.

200

201 In this manuscript, we focus on the use of an existing, externally developed conceptual DAG,
202 originally proposed to represent the population-level causal structure linking AFO-related
203 exposures to respiratory health outcomes, as a methodological tool for bias assessment in a

204 systematic review context. We do not modify the DAG or construct a synthesis or study-specific
205 DAG. Instead, we use the published DAG as a reference model to illustrate how different
206 adjustment choices reported in primary studies may open or close biasing paths under the
207 assumed causal structure. By doing so, we aim to demonstrate how DAG-based reasoning can
208 complement existing risk-of-bias approaches and provide greater conceptual transparency when
209 interpreting observational evidence on AFO exposures and community health.ALTHOUGH DAGS
210 WERE ORIGINALLY AND USUALLY USED FOR DESIGNING OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES OF
211 CAUSAL QUESTIONS, OUR OBJECTIVE WAS TO EXPLORE DAGS AS A BIAS
212 ASSESSMENT TOOL. GIVEN THE NEED TO ESTABLISH IF THERE EXISTS A CAUSAL LINK
213 BETWEEN RESIDING NEAR AFOS AND ADVERSE COMMUNITY HEALTH OUTCOMES, A
214 COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE ESTIMATES POST-ADJUSTMENT FOR
215 POTENTIAL CONFOUNDERS IS IMPORTANT. THIS INCLUDES UNDERSTANDING
216 WHETHER THE SET OF VARIABLES CONTROLLED BY RESEARCHERS ARE
217 CONFOUNDERS, MEDIATORS, OR COLLIDERS, AS INAPPROPRIATE ADJUSTMENTS MAY
218 INTRODUCE BIAS AND OBSCURE THE TRUE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EXPOSURE AND
219 HEALTH OUTCOMES. PROPERLY IDENTIFYING AND ACCOUNTING FOR CONFOUNDING
220 IS ESSENTIAL TO ENSURE THAT THE FINDINGS REFLECT ACCURATE CAUSAL
221 INFERENCES.
222

223 **OBJECTIVES**

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226 The objective of this study is to demonstrate how an existing, unmodified, population-level
227 directed acyclic graph (DAG) can be used as a reference framework for assessing potential
228 confounding and adjustment-related bias in evidence synthesis of observational studies that are
229 intended for, or commonly interpreted as, causal inference. Using published studies examining
230 associations between exposure to animal feeding operations (AFOs) and community respiratory
231 health as an illustrative example, we evaluate whether covariate adjustment strategies reported
232 in primary studies are compatible with the assumed population-level causal structure
233 represented by the DAG. The secondary objective is to evaluate whether primary studies
234 reported a rationale for covariate selection.

235 This work does not aim to derive a new causal model, construct a synthesis- or study-specific
236 DAG, or estimate causal effects. Rather, its purpose is methodological: to illustrate how DAG-
237 based reasoning may complement conventional risk-of-bias approaches in evidence synthesis by
238 improving transparency in the evaluation of confounding and inappropriate adjustment.THE
239 PRIMARY OBJECTIVE OF THIS STUDY WAS TO EVALUATE IF INCORPORATING A DAG
240 INTO THE BIAS ASSESSMENT FOR OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES ENABLED DETECTION OF
241 BIASING PATHWAYS DUE TO UNCONTROLLED CONFOUNDERS OR CONTROLLED
242 COLLIDER VARIABLES. AS THE CONTROL SETS AND PRESENCE OF BIASING PATHWAYS

243 MAY DIFFER DEPENDING UPON THE AIM TO ESTIMATE THE TOTAL OR DIRECT EFFECT,
244 WE HAD A SECONDARY OBJECTIVE TO EVALUATE WHAT RATIONALE THE AUTHORS
245 PROVIDED FOR SELECTING CONTROL VARIABLES AND IF THE GOAL WAS TO ESTIMATE
246 THE DIRECT OR TOTAL EFFECT OF RESIDING NEAR AN AFOS ON HUMAN HEALTH.

248 **METHODS**

249 Source of studies andThe sampling strategy

250 The studies included in this analysis represent a subset of those identified in a living systematic
251 review (LSR) assessing the health effects of Animal Feeding Operations (AFOs) on nearby
252 communities. The methods for the LSR, including search strategies, screening procedures, and
253 eligibility criteria, are described in a publicly available protocol~~We describe the methods for the~~
254 ~~review in the protocol published online ([https://syreaf.org/wp-](https://syreaf.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Draft_Protocol_CAF0-3.pdf)~~
255 ~~content/uploads/2022/05/Draft_Protocol_CAF0-3.pdf~~).

256 From the pool of studies identified through abstract and full-text screening, we selected
257 observational studies that evaluated associations between residential exposure to AFOs and
258 incident health outcomes, including outcomes affecting the lower respiratory tract, upper
259 respiratory tract, antibiotic resistance, gastrointestinal disease, and infectious diseases. Studies
260 were included if, based on reported analytic approach, the review team judged that the reported
261 effect estimates were intended to reflect the occurrence of new health events following
262 exposure. For the purposes of this demonstration, an incident outcome was defined as the first
263 occurrence of a lower respiratory disease event during follow-up among individuals initially free
264 of the outcome. Restricting inclusion to studies assessing incident outcomes ensured
265 appropriate temporality between exposure and outcome, a prerequisite for causal interpretation
266 and for constructing DAGs that reflect hypothesized causal ordering.

267 After abstract and full-text screening, we identified studies that used incident health
268 outcomes in a variety of organ systems (lower respiratory tract, upper respiratory tract,
269 antibiotic resistance, gastrointestinal disease, and infectious diseases) for this study.
270 The reason for the inclusion criteria is that causal inferences require incident events. The
271 determination of incidence events was based either on the study design (cohort design
272 or nested-cohort design) or an evaluation by the review team that the study met the
273 criteria, such that an effect measure reported should be interpreted as an incidence odds
274 ratio or risk ratio. Readers unfamiliar with this interpretation of prevalence studies or
275 case-control studies as designs that can estimate measures of comparative incidence
276 are directed to methodology studies that discuss this topic.

277 (Ferguson et al., 2020; Shrier and Platt, 2008; Williams et al., 2018)

279 Adoption of a population-level DAG for the review

280 For the purposes of this review, we adopted a single, population-level DAG to represent the
281 assumed causal structure linking residential exposure to AFOs and respiratory health outcomes
282 in nearby communities. Specifically, we adopted the DAG developed by Brewer et al. (2017) as
283 the synthesized causal model for the review. Throughout this review, 'residential exposure to
284 AFOs' is treated as the underlying exposure construct; study-specific measures such as self-
285 reported odor or modeled emissions are considered proxy operationalizations of this construct,
286 consistent with the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG. The Brewer et al. DAG was selected for three
287 reasons (Figure 1). First, it is, to our knowledge, the only published DAG explicitly developed for
288 the AFO community respiratory health context. Second, it was constructed using domain
289 expertise and background knowledge relevant to environmental exposures and respiratory
290 outcomes at the population level, rather than being tied to a specific study design. Third, the
291 DAG was developed independently of the present review, reducing the risk that it reflects post-
292 hoc adaptation to the included studies. The reference DAG was used without structural
293 modification. For clarity of presentation, its nodes were visually reorganized to emphasize a
294 temporal ordering. This visual reorganization was intended to aid interpretation and did not alter
295 the causal assumptions encoded in the DAG or introduce additional analytic steps.

296 By adopting this DAG, we make explicit the causal assumptions under which covariate
297 adjustment strategies in the included studies are evaluated. The DAG represents
298 population-level causal relationships and does not incorporate study-specific features such
299 as selection mechanisms or measurement error. This DAG represents causal constructs

300 rather than study-specific measured variables. Accordingly, variables reported in each
301 primary study (e.g., odor reports, distance to facilities, education) were evaluated as
302 imperfect proxies for these constructs and mapped to existing DAG nodes, rather than
303 introduced as separate measured nodes. The approach to the analysis of the primary
304 objective

305 The approach to evaluating if incorporating a DAG into the bias assessment for observational
306 studies enabled the detection of biasing pathways due to uncontrolled confounders or controlled
307 collider variables included steps:

- 308 1. ——— Based on the reporting in the methods and materials, identify the exposure variable, the
309 outcome variable and control variables included in the statistical model or the study design.
- 310 2. ——— Map the exposure variable, the outcome variable, and the control variables onto the
311 matching/proxy variable nodes used in either the proposed DAG or a previously published DAG.
- 312 3. ——— Recreate the DAG proposed by the authors of the observational study, or a previously
313 published DAG, in Daggitty software[®]. This should include the exposure node and outcome
314 node, and proposed pathways that may contain collider, mediator, and or confounding nodes.
- 315 4. ——— Indicate on the DAG, in Daggitty software, which variables are exposure, outcome, and
316 control variables.
- 317 5. ——— If the control variables from the statistical model or study design did not have
318 matching/proxy variable terms in the proposed DAG or a previously published DAG, add them
319 to the DAG as independent confounders, i.e., a common cause of the outcome and the
320 exposure.
- 321 6. ——— After indicating which variables were controlled, evaluate the DAG to determine if any
322 open biasing pathways remained
- 323 7. ——— Reach a conclusion about the potential for bias in the estimate based on the presence of
324 open biasing pathways which are indicated in the DAGitty software[®] with red pathways.

325 **Approach to the analysis of the primary objective**

326 For each included study, we assessed whether the variables reported as controlled would,
327 under the Brewer et al. DAG, block all non-causal (biasing) pathways between exposure and
328 outcome without introducing bias through inappropriate conditioning.

329 This assessment was based on principles of graphical causal analysis, using d-separation as
330 the criterion for determining whether sets of control variables were theoretically sufficient to
331 close backdoor paths while leaving causal pathways unblocked. Importantly, this evaluation is
332 independent of statistical significance, effect magnitude, or automated variable-selection
333 procedures. Instead, it relies on the theoretical compatibility between reported analytical
334 decisions and the assumed causal structure.

335 **Implementation of the DAG-based bias assessment**

336 For each included study, information was extracted from the Methods and Statistical Analysis
337 sections to identify the exposure variable(s), outcome variable(s), and all variables reported as
338 controlled through statistical adjustment, matching, restriction, or stratification. Study-specific
339 exposure measures (e.g., self-reported odor, distance to the nearest AFO, or density of AFOs)
340 were treated as proxies for the exposure construct represented in the adopted DAG. Similarly,
341 respiratory outcomes reported in individual studies were mapped to the outcome node in the
342 DAG based on conceptual equivalence.

343 Covariates adjusted for in each study were mapped to corresponding nodes in the DAG based
344 on conceptual meaning rather than exact terminology. When different labels were used across
345 studies (e.g., “household income,” “economic status,” or “poverty-to-income ratio”), these were
346 mapped to the appropriate socioeconomic construct represented in the DAG. When a reported
347 control variable could not be plausibly mapped to an existing node, it was treated as an
348 additional variable and considered in relation to the assumed causal structure.

349 Although the conceptual assessment of bias relied on graphical causal reasoning and the rules
350 of d-separation, the practical implementation of this assessment was supported using DAGitty
351 software (Textor et al., 2016). DAGitty was used to encode the adopted DAG, indicate
352 conditioned variables for each study, and systematically identify open backdoor paths. The use
353 of DAGitty served as an analytical aid rather than a requirement of the method; the underlying
354 logic of the assessment is independent of any specific software tool.

355 **Evaluation of confounding and inappropriate adjustment**

356 Using the mapped DAG for each study, we evaluated whether the reported covariate
357 adjustment strategy was theoretically sufficient to block non-causal (biasing) pathways between
358 exposure and outcome. This evaluation focused on identifying:

- potential uncontrolled confounding, indicated by open backdoor paths remaining after adjustment; and
- potential inappropriate adjustment, such as conditioning on variables that act as mediators or colliders within the assumed causal structure.

The assessment was structural and theoretical, relying solely on the causal assumptions encoded in the adopted DAG and the variables reported as controlled in each study. No re-estimation of effect sizes was performed, and no modifications were made to the adopted DAG.

Analytical assumptions

The approach illustrated in this study rests on several analytical assumptions that warrant explicit acknowledgement. First, it assumes the availability of a DAG that plausibly represents the relevant population-level causal structure linking exposure and outcome. Second, it assumes that at least some of the variables depicted in the DAG are observable and reported with sufficient clarity in primary studies to permit meaningful comparison of adjustment strategies. Third, it assumes a degree of methodological comparability across studies, particularly with respect to outcome definition, exposure operationalization, and analytical conditioning decisions, such that potential sources of confounding or collider bias can be evaluated in a consistent manner. These assumptions are treated as analytical priors for the illustrative review presented here.

Assessment of reporting rationale for covariate selection (secondary objective)

To address the secondary objective, we reviewed the Methods and Statistical Analysis sections of each included study to determine whether authors reported an explicit rationale for covariate identification, selection, or retention. A rationale was considered present if authors described *a priori* criteria, model-building strategies, or decision rules guiding covariate inclusion. Studies were classified according to whether such a rationale was reported. This assessment evaluated reporting practices only and did not judge the appropriateness of selected covariates.

THE ROLE OF THE BREWER-ET AL. (2017) DAG IN THE PRIMARY OBJECTIVE

THE PLANNED SOURCE OF THE DAG FOR PRIMARY OBJECTIVE WAS EITHER A DAG DEVELOPED AND PUBLISHED BY AUTHORS OF THE ELIGIBLE STUDIES OR A PREVIOUSLY PUBLISHED DAG. FOR STUDIES THAT REPORTED A LOWER RESPIRATORY DISEASE OUTCOME AND DID NOT REPORT THEIR OWN DAG, WE PLANNED TO USE THE BREWER-ET AL. (2017) DAG (FIGURE 1). THE BREWER-ET AL. (2017) DAG WAS USED AS IT IS THE ONLY PUBLISHED DAG WE COULD IDENTIFY FOR THIS ASSESSMENT, AS

392 DISCUSSED FURTHER IN THE RESULTS. A SHORT TUTORIAL ON THE DAGS USING THE
393 BREWER ET AL. (2017) DAG AS AN EXAMPLE IS AVAILABLE IN THE SUPPLEMENTARY
394 MATERIAL.

395 We did modify the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG to incorporate two considerations (Figure 2). First,
396 the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG incorporated mechanistic intermediary variables, which represent
397 factors involved in the causal pathway between an exposure and an outcome, as well as
398 diagnostic variables (Exhaled Nitric Oxide (biomarker)), which are indicators used in the
399 diagnosis or assessment of a condition. We excluded these elements. The direct path without
400 any intermediary variables (Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Chronic bronchitis) was removed because we
401 hypothesized that this pathway was captured by the mechanistic and diagnostic variables in the
402 following indirect pathway:

403 • (NH₃, H₂S) → Bronchial irritation → Lung inflammation → Exhaled Nitric Acid → Chronic
404 bronchitis

405 Second, the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG assumed that the node SES was not measurable;
406 therefore, it was labeled as an unobservable. However, as other researchers in this topic area
407 (AFOs and community health) have used SES as observable, we modified the DAG such that it
408 could be observable. This approach meant that SES was part of the minimum sufficient sets:

- 409 • Minimum sufficient adjustment set 1: Education Level
- 410 • Minimum sufficient adjustment set 2: Land Use/ Zoning
- 411 • Minimum sufficient adjustment set 3: Socioeconomic Status (SES)

412 None of these minimum sufficient adjustment sets were used preferentially and therefore any
413 exposure-outcome pair that controlled for a minimum sufficient set could be considered
414 unbiased, provided they did not also control for a collider variable.

415 While the DAG developed by Brewer et al. (2017) identified Chronic Bronchitis as the outcome
416 of interest, we considered it feasible to assume that other lower respiratory tract conditions
417 could share the same causal structure. Similarly, although the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG
418 designated the exposure of interest as odor, we considered other metrics of exposure to be a
419 proxy for “measures of odor,” such as density of AFOs or distance of residence from AFOs. The
420 rationale for this approach was that odor, density and distance are common exposure metrics in
421 this topic area, and we assumed that Brewer et al. (2017) DAG and the authors of the
422 observational studies do not truly think that odor, distance or density are the direct causes but
423 rather proxies for exposure to aerosol emissions when studying respiratory outcomes. Using

424 the DAGitty program, the subsequent DAG was assessed to identify remaining biasing
425 pathways and ascertain the feasibility of estimating either the total or direct causal effect (Textor
426 et al. 2016). As an illustration, we mapped all lower respiratory disease terms to Chronic
427 Bronchitis, and we mapped all measures of AFO exposure to Odors. Regarding controlled
428 variables, we attempted to match the terms used by the authors to variables in the Brewer et al.
429 (2017) DAG. For instance, if the authors referenced "household income," we mapped this
430 variable to SES in the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, designating it as an observable variable since
431 the authors adjusted for it implicitly. Another example, "smoking status and exposure to
432 secondhand smoke at home," was described as a confounding variable in one study and this
433 was mapped to Smoking. Similarly, in one study "economic status" was mapped to SES.

434 Following the mapping process, the resulting DAG was evaluated. We determined whether the
435 total effect or the direct effect (relevant only to the original DAG) was estimated and if any
436 biasing pathways were still open after the authors controlled for the confounders they identified.

437 **Planned approach to secondary objective**

438 For the secondary objective, we read the methods and materials for a rationale for inclusion as
439 a control variable. Similarly, we evaluated the manuscripts for a description from the authors of
440 the goal to estimate either the direct or total effect of exposure on the outcome.

441 **RESULTS**

442

443

444 **Study Identification and InclusionData collection**

445 The flow chart for the original systematic review is provided in the supplementary materials. The
446 original review found 36 studies that reported prevalent or incident outcomes. Of those 36
447 observational studies, 17 studies met the eligibility criteria for this methodological assessment,
448 namely the evaluation of incident health outcomes. None of the 17 included studies reported an
449 explicit causal diagram or articulated a causal model underlying their analytic approach. Key
450 characteristics of the included studies are summarized in Table 1.

451 The flow chart for the original systematic review is provided in the supplementary materials. The
452 original review found 36 studies that reported prevalent or incident outcomes. Within these 36
453 studies, 17 studies meet the eligibly criteria for this study i.e., evaluated an incident outcome.

454 **Results of Primary Objective**

455 Of the 17 studies, 10 examined lower respiratory tract outcomesOf the seventeen studies, none
456 provided a DAG or causal pathway for any outcomes. Therefore, it was only possible to assess
457 the primary objective for studies that reported an incident lower respiratory disease outcome, as
458 the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG was published and available for assessment. Ten studies
459 reported lower respiratory outcomes (Radon et al. 2005; Mirabelli et al. 2006; Hoopmann et al.
460 2006; Radon et al. 2007; Smit et al. 2012; Hoiveld et al. 2016 ; Freidl et al. 2017 ; Rasmussen
461 et al. 2017 ; Schultz et al. 2019 ; van Kersen et al. 2020). For these outcomes, the population-
462 level DAG published by Brewer et al. (2017) was available and served as the reference causal
463 structure for the primary analysis. One study focused on Q-fever-associated pneumonia (Smit
464 et al., 2012) and was excluded from DAG-based assessment because the causal pathway for
465 this outcome involves a distinct infectious mechanism not represented in the Brewer DAG. One
466 Dutch cohort study employed a self-controlled design in which each participant served as their
467 own control (van Kersen et al., 2020). This design estimates a within-person causal effect by
468 leveraging temporal variation in exposure and implicitly controls for all time-invariant
469 confounders by design. As such, the causal estimand targeted by this study differs
470 fundamentally from the between-person estimands addressed by the other included
471 observational studies. Because the adopted population-level DAG represents hypothesized
472 between-person causal relationships and confounding structures, it is not appropriate for
473 evaluating studies targeting within-person estimands. For this reason, the van Kersen et al.
474 (2020) study was not evaluated using the DAG-based framework applied to the remaining
475 studies.

476 The paper by Smit et al. (2012) studied pneumonia associated with Q fever was excluded, as
477 the causal pathway for Q fever is unique, involving exposure to the causal organism, and the
478 confounding pathway through SES to Q-fever-associated pneumonia seemed unlikely. In
479 another Dutch cohort study, each subject served as their own control (van Kersen et al. 2020).
480 Therefore, we assumed that all variables were controlled except, perhaps time. Since the DAG
481 by Brewer et al. (2017) did not include time as a factor, this study was not considered. This left 8
482 studies to evaluate against the modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG for the primary objective.
483 The 17 studies were all utilized for the secondary objective.

484

485

486 **Primary Objective Compatibility of Adjustment Strategies with the Reference DAG**

487 Table 2 summarizes the covariates adjusted for in each of the eight studies evaluated against
488 the reference DAG. Across studies, authors adjusted for a wide range of demographic,
489 environmental, and socioeconomic variables. Many of these variables were not represented in
490 the Brewer et al. DAG, reflecting differences between study-specific modeling choices and the
491 population-level causal structure proposed in the reference model.

492
493 When mapped descriptively to the reference DAG, none of the eight studies adjusted for a
494 complete set of variables that would theoretically block all non-causal pathways between AFO
495 exposure and lower respiratory outcomes under the assumed population-level structure (Figure
496 2). In several studies, adjustment sets omitted variables represented as common causes in the
497 reference DAG (e.g., socioeconomic position), while simultaneously including variables that
498 occupy non-confounding positions within that structure. The results of Steps 1 and 2 for the
499 primary objective are reported in Table 2, i.e. the control variables reported by the authors are
500 mapped to terms used for the nodes in the modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG. Other variables
501 were mapped as independent confounders with the following exceptions: for Radon et al. (2005)
502 we hypothesized that the allergy status of the parents impacted living near AFOs; for Hoopmann
503 et al. (2006) we added a new pathway (SES leads to “breastfeeding” leading to “asthma risk”);
504 for Schultz et al. (2019) we added a new pathway with “proximity to major road” (Zoning Use
505 causes “proximity to major roads” and “proximity to major roads” was a cause of Lower
506 Respiratory Disease and AFOs) (see the Supplementary Materials). In six of the eight studies,
507 smoking-related variables were included in the adjustment set (Radon et al. 2005; Mirabelli et
508 al. 2006; Hoopmann et al. 2006; Radon et al. 2007; Rasmussen et al. 2017; Schultz et al.
509 2019). In the reference DAG, smoking is positioned as a collider on at least one pathway linking
510 socioeconomic factors to respiratory outcomes. Conditioning on such a variable is therefore
511 theoretically incompatible with the causal structure assumed in the reference DAG and may
512 open biasing pathways under that model.

513 In the remaining two studies, neither smoking nor key socioeconomic variables were included in
514 the adjustment set (Freidi et al. 2017, Hooiveld et al 2016). Given that the reference DAG
515 represents a population-level structure and does not encode country-specific design features or
516 restrictions, it was not possible to determine whether these variables were implicitly controlled
517 through study design or population homogeneity. As a result, no definitive conclusion could be
518 drawn regarding compatibility with the reference DAG in these cases. Overall, none of the

519 evaluated studies reported adjustment strategies that were fully compatible with the population-
520 level causal structure represented by the Brewer et al. DAG.

521

522 **Results of Secondary Objective**

523 In all the 17 studies, researchers employed multivariable models and adjusted for potential
524 confounding variables. Among the 17 studies, only three provided a rationale for selecting and
525 retaining potential confounding variables. Schultz et al. (2019), Freidl et al. (2017), and Simões
526 et al. (2022) specified criteria for retaining covariates in the multivariable model, primarily based
527 on a change in the main effect estimate exceeding 10%. Additionally, Freidl et al. (2017)
528 mentioned that covariates with a p-value less than 0.15 were included in the multivariable
529 analyses. Freidl et al. (2017) and Simões et al. (2022) mentioned that three multivariable
530 models were developed with different covariates. Upon evaluation, they observed minimal
531 disparity in magnitude among the three adjusted models. Consequently, they selected the
532 model with the least number of confounding variables (age and gender) for reporting purposes.
533 The remaining references included potential confounding variables in their statistical model
534 without specifying their identification process or utilizing model-building strategies. In studies
535 examining diseases affecting various body systems (e.g., digestive and respiratory), no
536 evidence was found indicating different causal pathways or hypotheses.

537 For Steps 3 to 5, the DAGs after the mapping process are presented in Figures 2-9. For Radon
538 et al. (2005), the results of these steps are presented in Figure 2. The nodes that are white are
539 variables controlled in the DAG. For example, the control variables reported by Radon et al.
540 (2005) as higher education status and Second-hand smoke exposure, were mapped to
541 education level and smoking. For controlled variables such as age, gender, and number of
542 siblings, which did not have equivalent variables in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, were
543 included as independent confounders. The DAGs and the DAGitty code for all other studies are
544 included in the Supplementary materials.

545 For Steps 6 and 7, we evaluated the DAGs by looking for open biasing pathways which are
546 shown as red paths. Biasing pathways remained open in all eight studies (Radon et al. 2005;
547 Mirabelli et al. 2006; Hoopmann et al. 2006; Radon et al. 2007; Hooiveld et al. 2016 ; Freidl et
548 al. 2017 ; Rasmussen et al. 2017 ; Schultz et al. 2019). For example, in Figure 2, a biasing
549 pathway remains even after controlling for the variables included in the Radon et al. 2005
550 model. The open pathway is as follows: Socioeconomic status → Land use / Zoning → CAFO

551 → Exposure → Perception of health risk → Chronic individual stress → Increased susceptibility
552 to infection → Lung inflammation → Lower respiratory disease.

553 In six studies of the eight studies that could be evaluated in Step 6 and 7, it appeared that
554 control of measures of smoking introduced a spurious association between the exposure and
555 the lower respiratory disease outcome because the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG includes smoking
556 as a collider variable (Radon et al. 2005; Mirabelli et al. 2006; Hoopmann et al. 2006; Radon et
557 al. 2007; Rasmussen et al. 2017 ; Schultz et al. 2019).

558 In two studies conducted in the Netherlands (Freidl et al. 2017, Hooiveld et al 2016) the authors
559 neither adjusted for Smoking (the collider variable) nor for Education or Socioeconomic Status;
560 therefore, biasing pathways remained . However, we do consider it feasible that these variables
561 may be controlled by the study design rather than a statistical modeling approach, i.e., perhaps
562 the thresholds for Education and SES applied to populations in the US are not relevant to
563 European countries or are controlled by the population restriction to the Netherlands. For these
564 studies, it is not possible to reach a conclusion about the presence or absence of biasing
565 pathways.

566 According to the modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, all studies examining lower respiratory tract
567 outcomes exhibited unnecessary adjustments. Researchers consistently accounted for multiple
568 variables that were not identified as confounders in the original or modified Brewer et al. (2017)
569 DAG

570 **Secondary objective**

571 None of the 17 studies explicitly stated whether the objective was to estimate the total or direct
572 effect of AFO exposure on the outcome. In all the 17 studies, researchers employed
573 multivariable models and adjusted for potential confounding variables, indicating their intent to
574 estimate the causal effect of exposure on health outcomes while adjusting for potential
575 confounders. Among the 17 studies, only three provided a rationale for selecting and retaining
576 potential confounding variables. Schultz et al. (2019), Freidl et al. (2017), and Simões et al.
577 (2022) specified criteria for retaining covariates in the multivariable model, primarily based on a
578 change in the main effect estimate exceeding 10%. Additionally, Freidl et al. (2017) mentioned
579 that covariates with a p-value less than 0.15 were included in the multivariable analyses. Freidl
580 et al. (2017) and Simões et al. (2022) mentioned that three multivariable models were
581 developed with different covariates. Upon evaluation, they observed minimal disparity in
582 magnitude among the three adjusted models. Consequently, they selected the model with the

583 least number of confounding variables (age and gender) for reporting purposes. The remaining
584 references included potential confounding variables in their statistical model without specifying
585 their identification process or utilizing model-building strategies. In studies examining diseases
586 affecting various body systems (e.g., digestive and respiratory), no evidence was found
587 indicating different causal pathways or hypotheses.

589 **DISCUSSION**

590
591 In this study, we illustrated how an existing, population-level DAG can be used as a reference
592 framework to evaluate covariate adjustment strategies reported in observational studies included
593 in a systematic review. Applying the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG to studies examining associations
594 between exposure to animal feeding operations (AFOs) and lower respiratory outcomes, we found
595 that none of the evaluated studies reported adjustment sets that were fully compatible with the
596 causal structure assumed in the reference DAG. This observation held despite the widespread
597 use of multivariable adjustment and despite authors' apparent intent to control for confounding.
598 The visual reorganization of the reference DAG to highlight temporality was intended to improve
599 interpretability rather than to redefine confounder status, and all assessments remain conditional
600 on the original causal structure proposed by Brewer et al.

601 Specifically, when the modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG is taken as a reasonable
602 representation of the hypothesized causal relationships linking aerosol emissions from AFOs to
603 lower respiratory outcomes, all evaluated studies exhibited at least one remaining open pathway
604 or adjusted for variables whose role in the causal structure is ambiguous. Importantly, this does
605 not imply that the reported estimates are necessarily biased in truth; rather, it indicates that,
606 under the assumptions encoded in the reference DAG, the adjustment strategies used do not
607 clearly correspond to a minimum sufficient adjustment set. The results our primary objective
608 suggested that using DAGs are a useful tool to reveal remaining open biasing pathways, even
609 in studies that adjusted for purported confounders, in a way that other tools, such as those
610 proposed by Robins-E, do not. Our results showed that each study had remaining open biasing
611 pathways, despite adjustment for the purported confounding variables.

612 For our secondary objective, we observed a need to improve the reporting of justifications for
613 selecting confounding variables to control in models – perhaps by including a DAG to illustrate
614 how the authors envisioned the selected control variables as part of a minimum sufficient set

615 enabling an unbiased estimation of the effect of interest.

616

617 Implications of the findings of the primary objective

618 Our results suggest that if the modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG is a reasonable description of
619 the causal pathways between aerosol emission from AFO and lower respiratory disease, then
620 the results of observational studies of that topic may be biased. A recurrent illustration of this
621 issue involves smoking, which was frequently included as a covariate based on its well-
622 established association with respiratory disease. Under the assumed causal structure encoded
623 in the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, however, conditioning on smoking may open a non-causal
624 pathway between exposure and outcome. This example illustrates how adjustment decisions
625 that are epidemiologically intuitive can, under certain causal assumptions, complicate causal
626 interpretation. Importantly, our objective is not to determine whether smoking truly functions as a
627 collider in this setting, but to demonstrate how DAG-based reasoning allows reviewers to make
628 the implications of such adjustment choices explicit when evaluating potential sources of
629 bias. According to the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, adjusting for Smoking, a collider variable,
630 opens a backdoor pathway between the exposure (Odors) and the outcome (Chronic
631 Bronchitis), inducing a false association. This may explain the variation in effect magnitudes
632 observed across studies. It certainly does not seem intuitive to leave Smoking status
633 uncontrolled, and that is probably why so many authors controlled for this variable. However,
634 since no authors supplied a DAG or any other causal pathway information, all these studies are
635 missing the different hypothesized pathways compared to Brewer et al. (2017) (Martinez 2023).

636

637 The criteria to define a variable as a collider should not be guided only by the fact that two
638 arrows point to that variable. It's important to consider the broader context of the causal
639 relationships. In the case of Smoking, while it is influenced by both Chronic Individual Stress (a
640 descendant of Odors) and Education Level (which affects Chronic Bronchitis), its role as a
641 collider is specifically defined by its position on different causal pathways: one originating from
642 the exposure (Odors) and the other influencing the outcome (Chronic Bronchitis). In contrast,
643 Lung Inflammation and Chronic Individual Stress are not colliders in the context of the specific
644 relationship between Odors and Chronic Bronchitis. Although Lung Inflammation has two arrows
645 pointing to it (from Increased Susceptibility to Infection and Exhaled Nitric Oxide), it doesn't sit at
646 the intersection of two independent causal pathways involving both the exposure (Odors) and
647 the outcome (Chronic Bronchitis). Similarly, Chronic Individual Stress receives arrows from

648 Perception of Health Risk and Socioeconomic Status, but these pathways are part of the same
649 causal sequence originating from Odors and ultimately influencing Smoking and Chronic
650 Bronchitis. There is no independent pathway that would introduce bias by adjusting for Chronic
651 Individual Stress in this context. Thus, while Smoking acts as a collider by connecting
652 independent pathways between Odors and Chronic Bronchitis, Lung Inflammation and Chronic
653 Individual Stress do not, because they do not link independent paths that could create bias if
654 controlled for in this specific relationship. To us, this complex causal pathway which has
655 smoking as a collider variable is not expected and visualization of the biasing pathways using
656 DAGs was essential to assessment of bias. **Outcome-Specific Causal Structures and**
657 **Adjustment Practices**

658 Many studies covered a broad spectrum of health outcomes, encompassing respiratory,
659 gastrointestinal, and infectious conditions in a single study. Adjustment in these studies was
660 performed using the same set of covariates. However, it remains unclear how those identical
661 covariates could be considered confounding factors in the associations between residing near
662 an AFO and outcome categories beyond lower respiratory tract disease (Martinez 2023). For
663 instance, Hooiveld et al. (2016) studied gastroenteritis-presumed infection, asthma, and chronic
664 enteritis, adjusting for the same set of confounders (“age,” “gender,” “duration of registration,”
665 “number of inhabitants in the zip code area,” and “total surface area”) across all outcomes. It
666 remains uncertain whether the causal pathways for these outcomes were replicated using
667 DAGs, although such a modeling approach would seem reasonable. This observation does not
668 imply that such analyses are invalid, but rather that their interpretation would benefit from
669 clearer articulation of the causal assumptions underpinning each exposure–outcome
670 relationship. DAGs provide one mechanism for making those assumptions explicit and for
671 distinguishing between confounders, mediators, colliders, and proxies across different
672 outcomes.

673 The application of a population-level DAG highlights the importance of context when interpreting
674 confounding. The Brewer et al. (2017) DAG was developed to represent hypothesized causal
675 relationships in a U.S. setting and may not fully capture causal structures operating in other
676 countries. For example, a study conducted in the Netherlands did not identify socioeconomic
677 status, assessed as standardized household income, as a confounder of the association
678 between residential proximity to AFOs and respiratory outcomes. From a DAG-based
679 perspective, this discrepancy does not imply that SES is or is not a confounder in any absolute
680 sense, but rather that its role depends on how socioeconomic factors are assumed to influence

681 both exposure and outcome within a given context. Importantly, whether a variable functions as
682 a confounder is determined by the assumed causal structure, specifically whether it is a
683 common cause of exposure and outcome, rather than by empirical criteria such as changes in
684 effect estimates after statistical adjustment. This underscores that DAG-based bias assessment
685 evaluates compatibility with an assumed causal structure, not empirical confirmation of that
686 structure.As the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG was designed by scientists in the US, it is expected to
687 represent the situation in the US; it may not necessarily reflect conditions in countries outside
688 the US. This may explain why the study by Hooiveld et al. (2016) which was conducted in the
689 Netherlands, found that SES (assessed as “standardized household income”) was, on analysis
690 by the authors, found not to be a confounding variable in the relationship between lower
691 respiratory tract conditions and living near AFOs. While adjusting for candidate confounders is
692 just one approach to identifying potential confounders, the hypothesis of a confounding effect
693 arising from socioeconomic determinants gains traction from the observation that certain Dutch
694 studies reported stable estimates even after controlling for SES. This suggests that SES might
695 not exert significant confounding influence in Dutch studies, possibly indicating minimal variation
696 in SES across exposures (e.g., different distances from the nearest AFOs). Another hypothesis
697 that requires further exploration is the notion of a threshold effect for SES, implying that the
698 adverse health impacts of AFOs may become stronger when SES exceeds a certain threshold
699 value.

700

701 In contrast, many US studies may require adjustment for a SES metric to capture
702 socioeconomic disparities linked to people residing near AFOs. Researchers in the US
703 examining potential adverse health impacts related to AFOs note that these operations are
704 predominantly located in disadvantaged communities. The observed impact of AFO exposure
705 on asthma or other medical conditions might be confounded by the effects of determinants of
706 poor health prevalent in disadvantaged communities. While we were unable to determine the
707 absolute truth, a key conclusion of this study is that many authors in this field failed to provide
708 readers and policymakers with hypothetical causal pathways for their target population or the
709 rationale for their set of adjustments. Such transparency could enhance clarity on biases,
710 potentially elucidate observed disparities, and enhance the societal value of research on the
711 human health effects of proximity to AFOs (Martinez 2023).

712

713 **Precedent for the approach**

714 This study builds on prior work demonstrating the use of DAGs in evidence synthesis and bias
715 assessment. There are two precedents for what we have done in the current study—namely,
716 utilizing DAGs to assess bias in a review. In 2012, Polzer et al. created their own DAGs to
717 investigate the link between tooth loss and mortality in humans, for which they derived minimum
718 sufficient sets of confounding variables. They then performed a systematic review of the
719 literature and assessed the included studies based on whether they controlled for the
720 appropriate variables. This approach required mapping the variables controlled for in the studies
721 controlled onto the variables identified in the minimum sufficient sets by Polzer et al. 2012. In
722 2025, Tiwari et al. created and published their own DAG to estimate the effect of being small-
723 for-gestational-age on malnutrition in children under five years of age. The key difference
724 between the Polzer et al. (2012) and Tiwari et al. (2025) studies and the current study is that the
725 DAG we used was based on a previously published DAG, rather than one we constructed
726 ourselves. Others have suggested a formal approach to creating DAGs using evidence
727 synthesis methods (Ferguson et al. 2020).

728
729 Although these methods are similar, they are not the same, as we utilized a previously
730 developed DAG and had hoped to use DAGs proposed by the authors of the original studies if
731 available. We were fortunate that a study conducted by researchers at the Environmental
732 Protection Agency (EPA) explicitly outlined a DAG hypothesizing the association between
733 Chronic Bronchitis and residing near AFOs (Brewer et al. 2017). If no DAG had been available,
734 we likely would have adopted the approach of creating a DAG. We envision that reviewers
735 might propose a DAG in their proposal as part of bias assessment or search for a public one as
736 we did.

737

738 **Limitations of using DAGs for bias assessment**

739 Our study has some limitations, with the most significant being the utilization of DAGs for a
740 “treatment” (living near an AFO) that is not mutable. In reality, living near an AFO is not an
741 observable exposure, according to the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, while Odor was an observable
742 variable (Brewer et al. 2017). Technically, DAGs need variables that are both well-defined and
743 amenable to intervention(s) (Tennant et al. 2021). In observational studies of environmental
744 health, defining exposures can pose challenges. We have presumed that all exposure metrics

745 utilized, such as NH₃ or ammonia, pounds of hogs within 3 miles, etc., could potentially be
746 modifiable and clearly defined interventions. However, one may consider that the Brewer et al.
747 (2017) DAG is not a causal diagram under the current state of knowledge given the
748 inconsistency in exposure metrics across this body of work. This inconsistency raises concerns,
749 as ill-defined exposures may yield causal pathways without clear causal interpretations.

750 Second, in the absence of study-specific causal frameworks, we assumed a shared causal
751 structure for lower respiratory outcomes, including chronic bronchitis. This assumption is
752 necessarily provisional and may not hold across populations or disease subtypes. Our findings
753 therefore apply specifically to lower respiratory outcomes evaluated under the reference DAG
754 and should not be generalized to other health domains without additional causal modeling. ¶
755 the absence of authors providing a causal framework, we have biologically assumed the same
756 causal pathway for all lower respiratory tract diseases, including chronic bronchitis. However, it's
757 important to acknowledge that this pathway is hypothesized and may be incorrect. The findings
758 shown in the current study are specifically applicable to respiratory health events, omitting other
759 health events related to different body systems that have been extensively studied, such as
760 gastrointestinal conditions or mood disorders. Once again, our primary emphasis is on urging
761 authors of primary research to provide justification for adjusted variables. This would allow
762 readers to synthesize the findings more effectively and reach accurate conclusions (Martinez
763 2023). Our assessment evaluates compatibility with an assumed causal structure rather than
764 establishing the presence or absence of bias in a definitive sense. The identification of open
765 pathways or ambiguous adjustments reflects uncertainty about causal interpretation, not proof
766 that reported estimates are incorrect.

767
768 Although not the primary objective of this paper, our findings highlight the need to improve
769 reporting of justifications for choosing covariates to control in multivariable models, as
770 demonstrated by the results of the secondary objective. Although not the focus of this paper there
771 is a need to improve reporting of justifications for choosing confounding variables to control in
772 models as shown by the findings of the secondary objective. DAGs are an increasingly standard
773 method for representing the hypothesized causal relationships among the variables and
774 identifying the minimum sufficient set (Brewer et al. (2017); Tennant et al. 2021). For older
775 studies it might not be reasonable to expect a DAG to be used, as their use has only become
776 more common in the past decade. Further, scrutiny of reporting of variables controlled for in
777 multivariable regression analysis is fairly new. The Strengthening the Reporting of

778 Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) guidelines (Noah 2008; von Elm et al. 2008)
779 recommend in Item 7 that authors should "Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors,
780 potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable." Item 16
781 indicates that authors should "Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-
782 adjusted estimates and their precision (e.g., 95% confidence interval). Make clear which
783 confounders were adjusted for and why they were included." However, the guidance does not
784 include information about DAGs. While none of the authors of the included studies proposed
785 their own DAG, the incorporation and documentation of DAGs or a hypothesized causal
786 pathway guiding the selection of adjustment variables would have enhanced our understanding
787 of the causal relationships hypothesized by the authors. ~~The absence of reported DAGs was~~
788 ~~often coupled with insufficient or absent justification for the selection of potential confounders~~
789 ~~incorporated into the models.~~

790
791 Beyond the conceptual and reporting challenges discussed above, several residual sources of
792 bias remain even when a temporality-informed DAG is used to appraise covariate adjustment
793 strategies. First, residual confounding is likely due to unmeasured or poorly measured variables,
794 particularly when primary studies provide limited justification for covariate selection or lack
795 information on causal ordering. Second, selection bias may arise from study participation,
796 healthcare access, or analytic restrictions, including forms of endogenous selection that can
797 induce collider bias and are rarely reported. People may choose where to live based on health,
798 socioeconomic status, or related factors, which can affect both exposure to animal feeding
799 operations and respiratory health. While these residential self-selection processes are
800 conceptually represented in the reference DAG through upstream social determinants, they
801 were rarely measured or discussed in the reviewed studies. As a result, residual confounding
802 due to residential self-selection cannot be ruled out and is acknowledged as a remaining source
803 of bias. Third, substantial heterogeneity in exposure definitions, outcome ascertainment, and
804 measurement timing across studies limits the ability to verify assumed causal pathways or
805 ensure comparability of adjustment sets. Finally, DAG-based assessments cannot overcome
806 incomplete reporting of study design or analytic decisions in primary studies and should
807 therefore be interpreted as identifying possible, rather than definitive, sources of bias. Together,
808 these limitations highlight that DAG-based evaluations enhance transparency but do not
809 eliminate fundamental uncertainties inherent in observational evidence synthesis. Beyond
810 confounding and collider bias, DAGs can also be used to conceptualize other sources of bias

811 relevant to evidence synthesis, including selection processes related to study participation, loss
812 to follow-up, or conditioning on study inclusion, provided these mechanisms can be plausibly
813 represented within the assumed causal structure.

814

815 **Conclusions**

816 Confounding remains a central challenge in observational studies examining the health effects
817 of residential proximity to AFOs. This study demonstrates that incorporating DAGs into bias
818 assessment can highlight ambiguities in the causal interpretation of commonly used adjustment
819 strategies, particularly when causal assumptions are not explicitly stated. We do not conclude
820 that the existing literature is uniformly biased; rather, we conclude that its interpretation would
821 be strengthened by clearer articulation of hypothesized causal structures.

822 We encourage authors of future studies in this area to develop, discuss, and report their causal
823 diagrams or equivalent frameworks. Doing so would enhance transparency, facilitate more
824 informative evidence synthesis, and strengthen the contribution of this literature to public health
825 decision-making.

826 ~~Confounding poses a challenge to drawing valid causal conclusions within this body of~~
827 ~~research. Relying solely on multivariable models without extensive analysis for selection,~~
828 ~~identification, and retention of confounding variables, without using tools such as DAGs, may~~
829 ~~not fully address bias and could result in biased estimates due to adjustment for inappropriate~~
830 ~~variables. In particular, we note that no study successfully estimated the direct effect of~~
831 ~~residential AFO exposure on lower respiratory outcomes. Half of the studies adjusted for a~~
832 ~~collider variable, while the other half did not adjust for any confounder identified in the Brewer et~~
833 ~~al. (2017) DAG. We encourage authors of future studies in this area to develop, discuss, and~~
834 ~~report their causal diagrams. Doing so would explicitly describe your rationale for selecting and~~
835 ~~identifying confounding variables and other elements of the causal structure that may introduce~~
836 ~~bias.~~

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841

842 **Disclosure statement**

843 See EBT declarations documents

844

845

846 FIGURES

847

848

849 *Figure 1:* Directed acyclic graph (DAG) adapted from Brewer et al. (2017) illustrating hypothesized causal
 850 and biasing pathways linking exposure to animal feeding operation (AFO) emissions (operationalized as
 851 odors) and lower respiratory disease (chronic bronchitis). Arrows indicate assumed causal direction and
 852 temporal ordering between variables. The DAG includes contextual determinants (e.g., socioeconomic
 853 status, land use/zoning), exposure, intermediate biological and psychosocial processes, behavioral factors,
 854 and the health outcome. Causal pathways represent direct and indirect mechanisms through which
 855 exposure may influence disease, while non-causal (backdoor) pathways illustrate potential sources of
 856 confounding and collider bias. The DAG is used as a reference framework to evaluate covariate adjustment

857 strategies reported in primary studies, rather than as a synthesized or study-specific causal modelThe
 858 Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) proposed by Brewer et al. in 2017 was generated using DAGitty.net
 859 (Textor et al., 2011). It depicts the causal relationship between Odors from AFOs and the lower
 860 respiratory disease outcome Chronic Bronchitis. Nodes upstream from a specific variable are
 861 referred to as "ancestors," while nodes downstream are termed "descendants." This DAG
 862 classifies variables as exposure (green circle with inner triangle, e.g., Odor), outcome (blue circle
 863 with inner "I," e.g., Chronic Bronchitis), unobserved (indicated by gray circles, e.g., CAFO (EPA
 864 uses this term instead of AFO)), adjusted (illustrated by a white circle node, not shown), ancestor
 865 of outcome (blue circle), and ancestor of exposure (green circle). Green arrows represent
 866 unbiased causal paths whereas red arrows indicate biasing paths. Abbreviations: NH₃ =
 867 ammonia; H₂S = hydrogen sulfide. © Brewer et al (2017), used with permission under license
 868 number 5563820571671.

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879 [Figure 2. Directed acyclic graph \(DAG\) for Radon et al. \(2005\) mapped onto the Brewer et al. \(2017\)](#)
 880 [reference causal model. DAG illustrating the covariate adjustment strategy used by Radon et al. \(2005\),](#)
 881 [mapped onto the population-level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. \(2017\) for the association](#)
 882 [between exposure to animal feeding operation \(AFO\)–related emissions and lower respiratory disease.](#)
 883 [The DAG was recreated and evaluated using DAGitty.net.](#)

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887 [Figure 3. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Mirabelli et al., 2006, mapped onto the population-](#)
 888 [level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. \(2017\) for the association between exposure to animal](#)
 889 [feeding operation \(AFO\)–related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and](#)
 890 [evaluated using DAGitty.net. ** Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other outcomes](#)
 891 [reported were Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in past year, self-](#)
 892 [reported allergies, Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in past year all](#)
 893 [children, Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in the past year self-reported](#)
 894 [allergies. Other outcomes evaluated: Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization](#)
 895 [in past year, self-reported allergies, Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in](#)

896 past year all children, Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in the past year
897 self-reported allergies.

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900 Figure 4. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Hoopmann et al 2006, mapped onto the
901 population-level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure
902 to animal feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was
903 recreated and evaluated using DAGitty.net. ** Other outcomes assessed for this exposure are listed
904 below, as well as the model code. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other lower
905 respiratory outcomes reported were Allergic asthma-atopic parents, non-allergic asthma-non-atopic
906 parents, non-allergic asthma-Atopic parents, Asthmatic Pathology-Not-Atopic Parents, Asthmatic
907 Pathology-Atopic Parents, Asthmatic Pathology, IgE. Other outcomes evaluated: Allergic asthma-atopic
908 parents, non-allergic asthma-non-atopic parents, non-allergic asthma-Atopic parents, Asthmatic
909 Pathology-Not-Atopic Parents, Asthmatic Pathology-Atopic Parents, Asthmatic Pathology, IgE.

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 912 Figure 5. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Radon et al 2007, mapped onto the population-
 913 level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure to animal
 914 feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and
 915 evaluated using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other
 916 outcomes reported were: Bronchial Hyperresponsiveness to Methacholine, Physician-Diagnosed Asthma.
 917 Other outcomes evaluated: Bronchial Hyperresponsiveness to Methacholine, Physician-Diagnosed
 918 Asthma.

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 920 Figure 6. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Hooiveld et al 2016, mapped onto the population-
 921 level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure to animal
 922 feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and
 923 evaluated using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other
 924 outcomes reported were Physician-Diagnosed Asthma, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)

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 927 [Figure 7. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Freidl et al 2017, mapped onto the population-level](#)
 928 [causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. \(2017\) for the association between exposure to animal feeding](#)
 929 [operation \(AFO\)–related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and evaluated](#)
 930 [using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other outcomes reported](#)
 931 [were Physician-Diagnosed Asthma, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease \(COPD\). Other exposures](#)
 932 [evaluated: Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 1000m of residence. Presence of](#)
 933 [farm with minimum amount of animals within 1500m of residence, Presence of farm with minimum](#)
 934 [amount of animals within 2000m of residence, Distance \(quartiles expressed in meters\) between](#)
 935 [residence and closest farm with minimum 250 poultry, Distance \(quartiles expressed in meters\) between](#)
 936 [residence and closest farm with minimum 50 goats, Number of animals within 1000m of the residence,](#)
 937 [Number of farms \(any type\) within 1000m of residence.](#)

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 940 [Figure 8. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Rasmussen et al 2017, mapped onto the](#)
 941 [population-level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. \(2017\) for the association between exposure](#)

942 to animal feeding operation (AFO)–related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was
 943 recreated and evaluated using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide;
 944 SES = socioeconomic status. Other outcomes reported were Physician-Diagnosed Asthma, Chronic
 945 obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Other outcomes evaluated: Asthma emergency department
 946 visits, new asthma oral corticosteroid orders.

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949 Figure 9. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Schultz et al 2019, mapped onto the population-
 950 level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure to animal
 951 feeding operation (AFO)–related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and
 952 evaluated using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide; SES =
 953 socioeconomic status. Other outcomes reported were Nasal or lung allergies & current asthma. Current
 954 asthma. Asthma (at least 1 episode in past year). Asthma medication use in the past year. Physician-
 955 Diagnosed Asthma.

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 964 Figure 2: A modified Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) based on the one proposed by (Brewer et al.
 965 2017). The direct effect Odor → Chronic Bronchitis was removed, as well as the variable Exhaled
 966 Nitric Oxide (biomarker). Socioeconomic Status was mapped as an observable variable. The
 967 DAG was generated using DAGitty.net (Textor et al. 2011). Nodes upstream from a specific
 968 variable are referred to as “ancestors,” while nodes downstream are termed “descendants.”. This
 969 DAG classifies variables as exposure (Odor, green circle with inner triangle), outcome (Chronic
 970 Bronchitis), unobserved (gray circle), adjusted (white circle), ancestor of outcome (blue circle),
 971 and ancestor of exposure (green circle). Green arrows represent causal paths. Abbreviations:
 972 NH₃ = ammonia; H₂S = hydrogen sulfide. © Brewer et al (2017), used with permission under
 973 license number 5563820571671.

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979 Table 1: Characteristics of 17 relevant studies (listed chronologically from most recent)
 980 providing comparative estimates of the incidence of health outcomes and residential proximity to
 981 AFOs.

Study	Country	Exposure categories	Outcome categories
(Simões et al. 2022)	Netherlands	Number of livestock near the home	Lower respiratory
(Fisher et al. 2020)	US	Number of livestock near the home	Cancer
(van Kersen et al. 2020)	Netherlands	Levels of PM ₁₀ and NH ₃	Lower respiratory
(Schultz et al. 2019)	USA	Proximity of home to nearest AFO	Lower respiratory Upper respiratory
(Poulsen et al. 2018)	US	Poultry operation activity	Gastrointestinal condition
(Freidl et al. 2017)	Netherlands	Number of livestock near the home Distance of home from nearest AFO	Lower respiratory
(Rasmussen et al. 2017)	USA	Proximity of home to nearest AFO	Lower respiratory
(Hooiveld et al. 2016)	Netherlands	Number of AFOs near the home	Lower respiratory Upper respiratory Infectious condition Skin condition

Study	Country	Exposure categories	Outcome categories
(Nava Cortes et al. 2015)	Mexico	Proximity of home to an AFO	Infectious condition
(Levallois et al. 2014)	Canada	Density of livestock near the home	Gastrointestinal condition
(Schinasi et al. 2014)	US	Number of livestock near the home Proximity of home to an AFO Detected AFO odors while at home	Antimicrobial resistance
(Smit et al. 2012)	Netherlands	Number of livestock near the home Proximity of home to an AFO	Lower respiratory Infectious conditions
(Horton et al. 2009)	US	Pollution levels Odor rating	Psychiatric disorder
(Radon et al. 2007)	Germany	Odor rating Number of AFOs near the home	Lower respiratory
(Hoopmann et al. 2006)	Germany	Pollution levels	Lower respiratory
(Mirabelli et al. 2006)	USA	Density of livestock near school Odor rating Distance from nearest AFO	Lower respiratory

Study	Country	Exposure categories	Outcome categories
(Radon et al. 2005)	Germany	Proximity of home to nearest AFO Odor rating	Lower respiratory Upper respiratory

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987 Table 2. Summary of variables controlled for in relevant studies (listed chronologically from most
988 recent) that provide estimates of the incidence of lower respiratory tract conditions.

Study	Variables controlled
(Schultz et al. 2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)• Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)• Poverty to income ratio (mapped to SES)• Education (mapped)• BMI (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)• Smoking status (mapped to smoking)• Pet ownership (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)• Proximity to major roadways (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG. Analyzed as confounder and dependent of Zoning use)
(Freidl et al. 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)• Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)
(Rasmussen et al. 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Race/ethnicity (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)• Family history of asthma (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)

Study	Variables controlled
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smoking status (mapped to Smoking) • Medical Assistance (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Overweight/obesity (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Type 2 diabetes (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Community socioeconomic deprivation (mapped to SES) • Distance to nearest major and minor arterial road (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Squared distance to nearest major and minor arterial road (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Distance to nearest Geisinger hospital (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Squared distance to nearest Geisinger hospital (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Age category (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Sex (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Year of event (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)

Study	Variables controlled
(Hooiveld et al. 2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Age, polynomial (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Registry duration (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Number of inhabitants in the postal code area and total surface area (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)
(Radon et al. 2007)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active and Passive smoke exposure (mapped to smoking) • Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Level of education (mapped to education level) • Number of siblings (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Parental allergies (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Sex (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)
(Hoopmann et al. 2006)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Oldest sibling (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)

Study	Variables controlled
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experienced Street noise (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Actual smoking (mapped to smoking) • Education level (mapped onto education level) • Breastfed at least 4 months (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG. Analyzed as confounder and dependent of SES) • Mold (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Contact with cats at a young age not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG(not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Rug/carpeted floor (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)
(Mirabelli et al. 2006)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Use of gas stove (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Allergy status not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG(not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Hispanic ethnicity (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAGnot mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG)

Study	Variables controlled
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic status (mapped to SES) • Smoking status (mapped to smoking) • Exposure to secondhand smoke at home (mapped to smoking)
(Radon et al. 2005)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Allergies of parents (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>initially not mapped, then mapped as a cause of AFG) • Gender (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Higher education status (mapped to education level) • Second-hand smoke exposure (mapped to smoking) • Number of siblings (<u>not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG</u>not mapped in modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG) • Smoker-status (mapped to smoking)

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Figure 2 DAG generated for Radon et al, 2005 using DAGitty.net. The DAG allows variables to be labeled as exposure variables (green circle with inner triangle), outcome (blue circle with inner "I"), confounders (red light circle), and controlled variables (illustrated by a white circle node). Green arrows represent unbiased causal paths, and red arrows indicate biasing paths. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Model code is provided in the supplementary materials.

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1003 *Figure 3: DAG generated for Mirabelli et al., 2006 using DAGitty.net. The DAG allows variables to be*
 1004 *labeled as exposure variables (green circle with inner triangle), outcome (blue circle with inner "I"),*
 1005 *confounders (red light circle), and adjusted variables (illustrated by a white circle node). Green arrows*
 1006 *represent unbiased causal paths, and red arrows indicate biasing paths. ** Abbreviations: NH3 =*
 1007 *ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other outcomes reported where Asthma-related physician visit*
 1008 *emergency visit and/or hospitalization in past year, self-reported allergies, Asthma-related physician visit*
 1009 *emergency visit and/or hospitalization in past year all children, Asthma-related physician visit emergency*
 1010 *visit and/or hospitalization in the past year self-reported allergies.*

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1016 Figure 4: DAG generated for Hoopmann et al 2006 using DAGitty.net. The DAG allows variables to be
 1017 labeled as exposure variables (green circle with inner triangle), outcome (blue circle with inner "I"),
 1018 confounders (red light circle), and adjusted variables (illustrated by a white circle node). Green arrows
 1019 represent unbiased causal paths, and red arrows indicate biasing paths. ** Other outcomes assessed for
 1020 this exposure are listed below, as well as the model code. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen
 1021 sulfide. Other lower respiratory outcomes reported were Allergic asthma atopic parents, Non-allergic
 1022 asthma Non atopic parents, Non-allergic asthma Atopic parents, Asthmatic Pathology Not Atopic
 1023 Parents, Asthmatic Pathology Atopic Parents, Asthmatic Pathology, IgE.

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1028 *Figure 5:- DAG generated for Radon et al 2007 using DAGitty.net. The DAG allows variables to be labeled*
 1029 *as exposure variables (green circle with inner triangle), outcome (blue circle with inner "I"), confounders*
 1030 *(red light circle), and adjusted variables (illustrated by a white circle node). Green arrows represent*
 1031 *unbiased causal paths, and red arrows indicate biasing paths. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S =*
 1032 *hydrogen sulfide. Other outcomes reported were: Bronchial Hyperresponsiveness to Methacholine,*
 1033 *Physician Diagnosed Asthma.*

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1039 *Figure 6: DAG generated for Hooiveld et al 2016 using DAGitty.net. The DAG allows variables to be labeled*
 1040 *as exposure variables (green circle with inner triangle), outcome (blue circle with inner "I"), confounders*
 1041 *(red light circle), and controlled variables (illustrated by a white circle node). Green arrows represent*
 1042 *unbiased causal paths, and red arrows indicate biasing paths. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S =*
 1043 *hydrogen sulfide. The other outcomes reported were Physician Diagnosed Asthma, Chronic obstructive*
 1044 *pulmonary disease (COPD)*

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1049 *Figure 7. DAG generated for Freidl et al 2017 using DAGitty.net. Nodes that are “upstream” from a*
 1050 *particular variable are known as ancestors and nodes that are “downstream” from a particular variable*
 1051 *are decedents. The DAG allows variables to be labeled as exposure variables (green circle with inner*
 1052 *triangle), outcome (blue circle with inner “I”), confounders (red light circle), and adjusted variables*
 1053 *(illustrated by a white circle node). Green arrows represent unbiased causal paths and red arrows indicated*
 1054 *biasing paths. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide.*
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 1058 Figure 8. DAG generated for Rasmussen et al 2017 using DAGitty.net. The DAG allows
 1059 variables to be labeled as exposure variables (green circle with inner triangle), outcome (blue
 1060 circle with inner "I"), confounders (red light circle), and adjusted variables (illustrated by a white
 1061 circle node). Green arrows represent unbiased causal paths, and red arrows indicate biasing
 1062 paths. Other outcomes assessed were Asthma emergency department visits, New asthma oral
 1063 corticosteroid orders. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide.

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1065 *Figure 9 DAG generated for Schultz et al, 2019 using DAGitty.net. The DAG allows variables to be labeled*
 1066 *as exposure variables (green circle with inner triangle), outcome (blue circle with inner "I"), confounders*
 1067 *(red light circle), and adjusted variables (illustrated by a white circle node). Green arrows represent*
 1068 *unbiased causal paths, and red arrows indicate biasing paths. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S =*
 1069 *hydrogen sulfide. Other outcomes reported: Nasal or lung allergies & current asthma, Current asthma,*
 1070 *Asthma (at least 1 episode in past year), Asthma medication use in the past year, Physician-Diagnosed*
 1071 *Asthma.*

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1080 **REFERENCES**

- 1081 Bours, M.J.L., 2021. Tutorial: A nontechnical explanation of the counterfactual definition of effect
1082 modification and interaction. *J Clin Epidemiol* 134, 113–124.
- 1083 Churilov, L., Hayward, K., Yogendrakumar, V., Andrew, N., 2025. Conducting descriptive
1084 epidemiology and causal inference studies using observational data: A 10-point primer for
1085 stroke researchers. *Eur Stroke J* 23969873251332120.
- 1086 Correia, L.C.L., Mascarenhas, R.F., De Menezes, F.S.C., Oliveira, J.S., Vaccarino, V., Ross,
1087 J.S., Wallach, J.D., 2025. Confounder selection in observational studies in high-impact
1088 medical and epidemiological journals. *JAMA Netw Open* 8, e2524176–e2524176.
- 1089 Digitale, J.C., Martin, J.N., Glidden, D. V, Glymour, M.M., 2023. Key concepts in clinical
1090 epidemiology: collider-conditioning bias. *J Clin Epidemiol* 161, 152–156.
- 1091 Digitale, J.C., Martin, J.N., Glymour, M.M., 2022. Tutorial on directed acyclic graphs. *J Clin*
1092 *Epidemiol* 142, 264–267.
- 1093 Dijk, S.W., Caulley, L.M., Hunink, M., Labrecque, J., 2024. From complexity to clarity: how
1094 directed acyclic graphs enhance the study design of systematic reviews and meta-
1095 analyses. *Eur J Epidemiol* 39, 27–33.
- 1096 Ferguson, K.D., McCann, M., Katikireddi, S.V., Thomson, H., Green, M.J., Smith, D.J., Lewsey,
1097 J.D., 2020. Evidence synthesis for constructing directed acyclic graphs (ESC-DAGs): a
1098 novel and systematic method for building directed acyclic graphs. *Int J Epidemiol* 49, 322–
1099 329.
- 1100 Gail, M.H., Altman, D.G., Cadarette, S.M., Collins, G., Evans, S.J.W., Sekula, P., Williamson,
1101 E., Woodward, M., 2019. Design choices for observational studies of the effect of exposure
1102 on disease incidence. *BMJ Open* 9, e031031.
- 1103 Hernán, M.A., Robins, J.M., 2020. Causal Inference: What If.
- 1104 Knol, M.J., Vandenbroucke, J.P., Scott, P., Egger, M., 2008. What do case-control studies
1105 estimate? Survey of methods and assumptions in published case-control research. *Am J*
1106 *Epidemiol* 168, 1073–81. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwn217>
- 1107 Parra, C.O., Bertizzolo, L., Schroter, S., Dechartres, A., Goetghebeur, E., 2021. Consistency of
1108 causal claims in observational studies: a review of papers published in a general medical
1109 journal. *BMJ Open* 11, e043339.

- 1110 Pearce, N., 2004. Effect measures in prevalence studies. *Environ Health Perspect* 112, 1047–
1111 50. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.6927>
- 1112 Reichenheim, M.E., Coutinho, E.S.F., 2010. Measures and models for causal inference in
1113 cross-sectional studies: arguments for the appropriateness of the prevalence odds ratio
1114 and related logistic regression. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 10, 66.
1115 <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-10-66>
- 1116 Sauer, B., VanderWeele, T.J., 2013. Use of directed acyclic graphs, in: *Developing a Protocol
1117 for Observational Comparative Effectiveness Research: A User's Guide*. Agency for
1118 Healthcare Research and Quality (US).
- 1119 Shrier, I., Platt, R.W., 2008. Reducing bias through directed acyclic graphs. *BMC Med Res
1120 Methodol* 8, 70.
- 1121 Tennant, P.W.G., Murray, E.J., Arnold, K.F., Berrie, L., Fox, M.P., Gadd, S.C., Harrison, W.J.,
1122 Keeble, C., Ranker, L.R., Textor, J., 2021. Use of directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) to
1123 identify confounders in applied health research: review and recommendations. *Int J
1124 Epidemiol* 50, 620–632.
- 1125 Williams, T.C., Bach, C.C., Matthiesen, N.B., Henriksen, T.B., Gagliardi, L., 2018. Directed
1126 acyclic graphs: a tool for causal studies in paediatrics. *Pediatr Res* 84, 487–493.
1127
- 1128 Arksey, H.; O'Malley, L. Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International
1129 Journal of Social Research Methodology* 2005;8:19-32
- 1130 Borlee, F.; Yzermans, C.J.; van Dijk, C.E.; Heederik, D.; Smit, L.A. Increased respiratory
1131 symptoms in COPD patients living in the vicinity of livestock farms. *Eur Respir J*
1132 2015;46:1605-1614
- 1133 Brewer, L.E.; Wright, J.M.; Rice, G.; Neas, L.; Teuschler, L. Causal inference in cumulative risk
1134 assessment: The roles of directed acyclic graphs. *Environ Int* 2017;102:30-41
- 1135 Cole, D.; Todd, L.; Wing, S. Concentrated swine feeding operations and public health: a review
1136 of occupational and community health effects. *Environ Health Perspect* 2000;108:685-
1137 699
- 1138 Cole, S.R.; Platt, R.W.; Schisterman, E.F.; Chu, H.; Westreich, D.; Richardson, D.; Poole, C.
1139 Illustrating bias due to conditioning on a collider. *Int J Epidemiol* 2010;39:417-420

1140 Didelez, V.; Stensrud, M.J. On the logic of collapsibility for causal effect measures. *Biom J*
1141 2022;64:235-242

1142 Dijk, S.W., Caulley, L.M., Hunink, M., Labrecque, J., 2024. From complexity to clarity: how
1143 directed acyclic graphs enhance the study design of systematic reviews and meta-
1144 analyses. *Eur J Epidemiol* 39, 27–33

1145 Douglas, P.; Robertson, S.; Gay, R.; Hansell, A.L.; Gant, T.W. A systematic review of the public
1146 health risks of bioaerosols from intensive farming. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*
1147 2018;221:134-173

1148 Ferguson, K.D.; McCann, M.; Katikireddi, S.V.; Thomson, H.; Green, M.J.; Smith, D.J.; Lewsey,
1149 J.D. Evidence synthesis for constructing directed acyclic graphs (ESC-DAGs): a novel
1150 and systematic method for building directed acyclic graphs. *Int J Epidemiol* 2020;49:322-
1151 329

1152 Fisher, J.A.; Freeman, L.E.B.; Hofmann, J.N.; Blair, A.; Parks, C.G.; Thorne, P.S.; Ward, M.H.;
1153 Jones, R.R. Residential Proximity to Intensive Animal Agriculture and Risk of
1154 Lymphohematopoietic Cancers in the Agricultural Health Study. *Epidemiology*
1155 (Cambridge, Mass) 2020;31:478-489

1156 Freidl, G.S.; Spruijt, I.T.; Borlee, F.; Smit, L.A.M.; Gageldonk-Lafeber, A.B.v.; Heederik, D.J.J.;
1157 Yzermans, J.; Dijk, C.E.v.; Maassen, C.B.M.; Hoek, W.v.d. Livestock-associated risk
1158 factors for pneumonia in an area of intensive animal farming in the Netherlands. *PLoS*
1159 *ONE* 2017;12:e0174796

1160 Guo, Y.; Ryan, U.; Feng, Y.; Xiao, L. Association of Common Zoonotic Pathogens With
1161 Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations. *Front Microbiol* 2021;12:810142

1162 Higgins, J.P.T.; Morgan, R.L.; Rooney, A.A.; Taylor, K.W.; Thayer, K.A.; Silva, R.A.; Lemeris,
1163 C.; Akl, E.A.; Bateson, T.F.; Berkman, N.D.; Glenn, B.S.; Hrobjartsson, A.; LaKind, J.S.;
1164 McAleenan, A.; Meerpohl, J.J.; Nachman, R.M.; Obbagy, J.E.; O'Connor, A.; Radke,
1165 E.G.; Savovic, J.; Schunemann, H.J.; Shea, B.; Tilling, K.; Verbeek, J.; Viswanathan, M.;
1166 Sterne, J.A.C. A tool to assess risk of bias in non-randomized follow-up studies of
1167 exposure effects (ROBINS-E). *Environ Int* 2024;186:108602

1168 Hooiveld, M.; Smit, L.A.M.; Sman-de Beer, F.v.d.; Wouters, I.M.; Dijk, C.E.v.; Spreeuwenberg,
1169 P.; Heederik, D.J.J.; Yzermans, C.J. Doctor-diagnosed health problems in a region with
1170 a high density of concentrated animal feeding operations: a cross-sectional study.
1171 *Environmental Health* 2016;15:(17 February 2016)

1172 Hoopmann, M.; Hehl, O.; Neisel, F.; Werfel, T. Associations between bioaerosols coming from
1173 livestock facilities and asthmatic symptoms in children. *Gesundheitswesen*

1174 (Bundesverband der Ärzte des Öffentlichen Gesundheitsdienstes (Germany))
1175 2006;68:575-584

1176 Horton, R.A.; Wing, S.; Marshall, S.W.; Brownley, K.A. Malodor as a trigger of stress and
1177 negative mood in neighbors of industrial hog operations. *American journal of public*
1178 *health* 2009;99:S610-S615

1179 Huitfeldt, A.; Stensrud, M.J.; Suzuki, E. On the collapsibility of measures of effect in the
1180 counterfactual causal framework. *Emerg Themes Epidemiol* 2019;16:1

1181 Knol, M.J., Vandenbroucke, J.P., Scott, P., Egger, M., 2008. What do case-control studies
1182 estimate? Survey of methods and assumptions in published case-control research. *Am J*
1183 *Epidemiol* 168, 1073–81. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwn217>

1184 Levac, D.; Colquhoun, H.; O'Brien, K.K. Scoping studies: advancing the methodology.
1185 *Implement Sci* 2010;5:69

1186 Levallois, P.; Chevalier, P.; Gingras, S.; Dery, P.; Payment, P.; Michel, P.; Rodriguez, M. Risk of
1187 infectious gastroenteritis in young children living in quebec rural areas with intensive
1188 animal farming: results of a case-control study (2004-2007). *Zoonoses and Public Health*
1189 2014;61:28-38

1190 Martinez, B.A.F. Animal Feeding Operations and Health Effects on People Living in the
1191 Surrounding Areas: A Comprehensive Analysis. . Department of Large Animal Clinician
1192 Sciences: Michigan State University 2023

1193 McElroy, K.G. Environmental health effects of concentrated animal feeding operations:
1194 implications for nurses. *Nurs Adm Q* 2010;34:311-319

1195 Mirabelli, M.C.; Wing, S.; Marshall, S.W.; Wilcosky, T.C. Asthma symptoms among adolescents
1196 who attend public schools that are located near confined swine feeding operations.
1197 *Pediatrics* 2006;118:e66-e75

1198 Moore, T.C.; Fong, J.; Rosa Hernandez, A.M.; Pogreba-Brown, K. CAFOs, novel influenza, and
1199 the need for One Health approaches. *One Health* 2021;13:100246

1200 Nava Cortes, N.; Romero Nunez, C.; Bautista Gomez, L.G.; Hernandez Garcia, P.A.; Heredia
1201 Cardenas, R. Presence of anti-Toxocara canis antibodies and risk factors in children
1202 from the Amecameca and Chalco regions of Mexico. *BMC Pediatrics* 2015;15:(30 May
1203 2015)

1204 Noah, N. The STROBE initiative: STrengthening the Reporting of OBServational studies in
1205 Epidemiology (STROBE). *Epidemiol Infect* 2008;136:865

1206 O'Connor, A.M.; Auvermann, B.; Bickett-Weddle, D.; Kirkhorn, S.; Sargeant, J.M.; Ramirez, A.;
1207 Von Essen, S.G. The association between proximity to animal feeding operations and
1208 community health: a systematic review. *PLoS One* 2010;5:e9530

1209 O'Connor, A.M.; Auvermann, B.W.; Dzikamuhenga, R.S.; Glanville, J.M.; Higgins, J.P.T.;
1210 Kirychuk, S.P.; Sargeant, J.M.; Totton, S.C.; Wood, H.; Von Essen, S.G. Updated
1211 systematic review: associations between proximity to animal feeding operations and
1212 health of individuals in nearby communities. *Syst Rev* 2017;6:86

1213 O'Connor, A.M.; Auvermann, B.W.; Higgins, J.P.; Kirychuk, S.P.; Sargeant, J.M.; Von Essen,
1214 S.G.; Glanville, J.M.; Wood, H. The association between proximity to animal-feeding
1215 operations and community health: a protocol for updating a systematic review. *Syst Rev*
1216 2014;3:99

1217 Pearce, N., 2004. Effect measures in prevalence studies. *Environ Health Perspect* 112, 1047–
1218 50. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.6927>

1219 Polzer, I.; Schwahn, C.; Volzke, H.; Mundt, T.; Biffar, R. The association of tooth loss with all-
1220 cause and circulatory mortality. Is there a benefit of replaced teeth? A systematic review
1221 and meta-analysis. *Clin Oral Investig* 2012;16:333-351

1222 Poulsen, M.N.; Pollak, J.; Sills, D.L.; Casey, J.A.; Rasmussen, S.G.; Nachman, K.E.; Cosgrove,
1223 S.E.; Stewart, D.; Schwartz, B.S. Residential proximity to high-density poultry operations
1224 associated with campylobacteriosis and infectious diarrhea. *International Journal of*
1225 *Hygiene and Environmental Health* 2018;221:323-333

1226 Radon, K.; Schulze, A.; Ehrenstein, V.; van Strien, R.T.; Praml, G.; Nowak, D. Environmental
1227 exposure to confined animal feeding operations and respiratory health of neighboring
1228 residents. *Epidemiology* 2007:300-308

1229 Radon, K.; Schulze, A.; Strien, R.; Ehrenstein, V.; Praml, G.; Nowak, D. [Prevalence of
1230 respiratory symptoms and diseases in neighbours of large-scale farming in Northern
1231 Germany]. *Pneumologie* 2005;59:897-900

1232 Rasmussen, S.G.; Casey, J.A.; Bandeen-Roche, K.; Schwartz, B.S. Proximity to Industrial Food
1233 Animal Production and Asthma Exacerbations in Pennsylvania, 2005-2012. *International*
1234 *journal of environmental research and public health* 2017;14

1235 Reichenheim, M.E., Coutinho, E.S.F., 2010. Measures and models for causal inference in
1236 cross-sectional studies: arguments for the appropriateness of the prevalence odds ratio
1237 and related logistic regression. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 10, 66.
1238 <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-10-66>

1239 Savitz, D.A.; Wellenius, G.A. Can Cross-Sectional Studies Contribute to Causal Inference? It
1240 Depends. *Am J Epidemiol* 2023;192:514-516

1241 Schinasi, L.; Wing, S.; Augustino, K.L.; Ramsey, K.M.; Nobles, D.L.; Richardson, D.B.; Price,
1242 L.B.; Aziz, M.; MacDonald, P.D.M.; Stewart, J.R. A case control study of environmental
1243 and occupational exposures associated with methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*
1244 nasal carriage in patients admitted to a rural tertiary care hospital in a high density swine
1245 region. *Environmental Health* 2014;13:1-12

1246 Schultz, A.A.; Peppard, P.; Gangnon, R.E.; Malecki, K.M.C. Residential proximity to
1247 concentrated animal feeding operations and allergic and respiratory disease.
1248 *Environment International* 2019;130:104911

1249 Simões, M.; Janssen, N.; Heederik, D.J.J.; Smit, L.A.M.; Vermeulen, R.; Huss, A. Residential
1250 proximity to livestock animals and mortality from respiratory diseases in The
1251 Netherlands: A prospective census-based cohort study. *Environment international*
1252 2022;161:107140

1253 Smit, L.A.; Hooiveld, M.; van der Sman-de Beer, F.; Opstal-van Winden, A.W.; Beekhuizen, J.;
1254 Wouters, I.M.; Yzermans, C.J.; Heederik, D. Air pollution from livestock farms, and
1255 asthma, allergic rhinitis and COPD among neighbouring residents. *Occup Environ Med*
1256 2014;71:134-140

1257 Smit, L.A.M.; van der Sman-de Beer, F.; Opstal-van Winden, A.W.J.; Hooiveld, M.; Beekhuizen,
1258 J.; Wouters, I.M.; Yzermans, J.; Heederik, D. Q fever and pneumonia in an area with a
1259 high livestock density: a large population-based study. *PloS one* 2012;7:e38843

1260 Sweeten, J.; Miner, R.; Tengman, C. Fact Sheet #1: A Brief History and Background of the EPA
1261 CAFO Rule in: curriculum R.f.L.a.P.E.S., ed; 2003

1262 Tennant, P.W.G.; Murray, E.J.; Arnold, K.F.; Berrie, L.; Fox, M.P.; Gadd, S.C.; Harrison, W.J.;
1263 Keeble, C.; Ranker, L.R.; Textor, J.; Tomova, G.D.; Gilthorpe, M.S.; Ellison, G.T.H. Use
1264 of directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) to identify confounders in applied health research:
1265 review and recommendations. *Int J Epidemiol* 2021;50:620-632

1266 Textor, J.; Hardt, J.; Knuppel, S. DAGitty: a graphical tool for analyzing causal diagrams.
1267 *Epidemiology* 2011;22:745

1268 Textor, J.; van der Zander, B.; Gilthorpe, M.S.; Liskiewicz, M.; Ellison, G.T. Robust causal
1269 inference using directed acyclic graphs: the R package 'dagitty'. *Int J Epidemiol*
1270 2016;45:1887-1894

1271 Tiwari S, Chhapola V, Chaudhary N, Sharma L. Directed acyclic graph helps to understand the
1272 causality of malnutrition in under-5 children born small for gestational age. *J Clin*

1273 Epidemiol. 2025 Jan;177:111611. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2024.111611. Epub 2024 Nov
1274 16. PMID: 39551398
1275 Thu, K.M. Public health concerns for neighbors of large-scale swine production operations. J
1276 Agric Saf Health 2002;8:175-184
1277 van Kersen, W.; Oldenwening, M.; Aalders, B.; Bloemsma, L.D.; Borlee, F.; Heederik, D.; Smit,
1278 L.A.M. Acute respiratory effects of livestock-related air pollution in a panel of COPD
1279 patients. Environment international 2020;136:105426
1280 von Elm, E.; Altman, D.G.; Egger, M.; Pocock, S.J.; Gotsche, P.C.; Vandenbroucke, J.P.;
1281 Initiative, S. The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology
1282 (STROBE) statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies. J Clin Epidemiol
1283 2008;61:344-349
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1286 **SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL**

1287

1288 **Illustration of DAG concepts using the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG**

1289 To illustrate how directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) were used in this study, we use the DAG
1290 published by Brewer et al. (2017), which hypothesizes causal relationships between exposure to
1291 emissions from animal feeding operations (AFOs), operationalized as odors, and lower
1292 respiratory disease, operationalized as chronic bronchitis (Figure 1). This DAG was used as an
1293 illustrative example to demonstrate key causal concepts relevant to bias assessment in
1294 observational studies.

1295 The Brewer et al. (2017) DAG includes different types of variables (nodes) and directed edges
1296 that represent hypothesized causal relationships between upstream contextual factors,
1297 exposure, intermediate processes, and the health outcome. In DAGs, arrows encode temporal
1298 and causal ordering, such that a parent node is assumed to precede its child node in time and
1299 cannot be caused by it. Although DAGitty does not assign explicit time stamps, temporality is
1300 enforced by the direction of arrows and the requirement that the graph remains acyclic.

1301 **Causal pathways and temporality**

1302 Within the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, causal pathways represent direct or indirect mechanisms
1303 through which exposure may influence the outcome, while biasing (non-causal) pathways
1304 connect exposure and outcome through alternative routes that may introduce confounding or
1305 collider bias.

1306 The DAG includes a **direct causal pathway**, represented as:

- 1307 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Chronic Bronchitis

1308 This pathway encodes the assumption that exposure precedes disease onset and does not
1309 involve intermediate variables.

1310 The DAG also specifies several indirect causal pathways, which represent temporally ordered
1311 sequences of events through intermediate variables, for example:

- 1312 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Bronchial irritation → Lung inflammation → Exhaled Nitric Oxide →
1313 Chronic Bronchitis
- 1314 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress → Smoking
1315 → Chronic Bronchitis

- 1316 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress → Smoking
1317 → Lung inflammation → Exhaled Nitric Oxide → Chronic Bronchitis

1318 Together, the direct and indirect causal pathways constitute the **total causal effect** of exposure
1319 on the outcome. Temporality is encoded through the directionality of the arrows, ensuring that
1320 exposure precedes perception, stress, behavior, biological changes, and ultimately disease.

1321 **Biasing pathways and confounding**

1322 The DAG also includes **biasing (backdoor) pathways**, which are **non-causal routes** linking
1323 exposure and outcome through common causes. For example:

- 1324 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) ← AFO ← Land Use/Zoning ← Socioeconomic Status (SES) →
1325 Education Level → Smoking → Chronic Bronchitis

1326 In this pathway, SES is a potential confounder because it influences both proximity to AFOs (via
1327 land use and zoning decisions) and downstream determinants of respiratory health, such as
1328 education and smoking. In DAG terminology, this represents a *backdoor path* connecting the
1329 exposure and outcome. To estimate the causal effect of exposure on outcome, such paths must
1330 be blocked, typically by conditioning on appropriate confounding variables.

1331 **Colliders and collider bias**

1332 The Brewer et al. (2017) DAG also illustrates **collider structures**. For example:

- 1333 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress → Smoking
1334 ← Education Level ← SES

1335 In this structure, Smoking is a collider because it has two incoming arrows from independent
1336 causal pathways: one originating from exposure-related stress and the other from
1337 socioeconomic determinants via education. Conditioning on a collider (e.g., adjusting for
1338 smoking in a regression model) can open an otherwise closed path between exposure and
1339 outcome, inducing a spurious association—this is known as **collider bias** (Cole et al., 2010;
1340 Digitale et al., 2023).

1341 Importantly, collider status cannot be inferred solely from the presence of two incoming arrows;
1342 it depends on whether those arrows represent independent pathways connecting exposure and
1343 outcome. In contrast, variables such as Lung Inflammation or Chronic Individual Stress,
1344 although they receive multiple arrows, do not act as colliders in this specific exposure–outcome
1345 relationship because they lie along a single causal sequence rather than at the intersection of
1346 independent paths.

1347 **Mediators and target causal effects**

1348 Some variables in the DAG function as mediators, meaning they lie on the causal pathway
1349 between exposure and outcome. For example:

- 1350 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress → Smoking
1351 → Chronic Bronchitis

1352 Perception of health risk and chronic stress are mediators in this pathway. Conditioning on
1353 mediators blocks part of the causal effect and therefore prevents estimation of the total effect,
1354 yielding instead an estimate closer to the direct effect. Adjusting for mediators is not inherently
1355 incorrect, but it must be aligned with the study's causal estimand and explicitly justified (Tennant
1356 et al., 2021).

1357 **Minimum sufficient adjustment sets**

1358 A **minimum sufficient adjustment set** is the smallest set of variables that, when conditioned
1359 on, blocks all non-causal (backdoor) paths between exposure and outcome without blocking
1360 causal pathways or opening collider paths. Identification of such sets involves examining all
1361 paths connecting exposure and outcome in the DAG and selecting variables that close
1362 confounding paths while preserving causal ones.

1363 In the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, multiple minimum sufficient adjustment sets exist for estimating
1364 the total causal effect of AFO exposure on chronic bronchitis. Specifically, either of the following
1365 single-variable sets is sufficient:

- 1366 • Minimum sufficient adjustment set 1: Education Level
- 1367 • Minimum sufficient adjustment set 2: Land Use/Zoning

1368 The existence of multiple valid adjustment sets reflects the structure of the hypothesized causal
1369 relationships and offers alternative strategies depending on data availability and feasibility. If
1370 AFO presence itself is unobserved, as assumed in the original Brewer et al. (2017) DAG,
1371 adjusting for either education level or land use/zoning is sufficient to block the relevant backdoor
1372 paths and obtain an unbiased estimate of the total effect under the assumed causal structure.

1373 **DISCUSSION OF THE DAGS WITH THE BREWER ET AL. (2017) AS AN EXAMPLE**

1374 To illustrate the use of DAGs, the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG relating an exposure (Odors from
1375 AFOs) and an outcome (Chronic Bronchitis) is provided in Figure 1. The Brewer et al. (2017)
1376 DAG contains different types of variables (node) and their relationships to exposure node and

1377 outcome node, as well as hypothesized causal and biasing pathways for the total effect and
1378 direct effects of Odors from AFOs. A causal pathway reflects the direct or indirect influence of
1379 an exposure on an outcome, while biasing pathways are non-causal routes that connect the
1380 exposure to the outcome through variables that can introduce confounding, collider bias, or
1381 inappropriate control of mediators, resulting in incorrect effect estimates.

1382 The direct causal effect in the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG is based on a pathway from odors to
1383 Chronic Bronchitis that does not pass through any intermediate variables (Odors (NH₃, H₂S) →
1384 Chronic Bronchitis).

1385 The Brewer et al. (2017) DAG also includes indirect causal pathways such as:

- 1386 ● AFO emissions (Odors (NH₃, H₂S)) → Bronchial irritation → Lung inflammation → Exhaled
1387 Nitric Acid → Chronic bronchitis
- 1388 ● AFO emissions (Odors (NH₃, H₂S)) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress
1389 → Smoking → Chronic Bronchitis
- 1390 ● AFO emissions (Odors (NH₃, H₂S)) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress
1391 ● → Smoking → Lung Inflammation → Exhaled Nitric Acid → Chronic Bronchitis

1392 The total causal effect would result from all causal pathways.

1393 Bias pathways include:

- 1394 ● AFO emissions (Odors (NH₃, H₂S)) ← AFO (CAFO) ← Land use/Zoning ← SES →
1395 Education Level → Smoking → Chronic Bronchitis.

1396 Socioeconomic Status (SES) is a potential confounder because it can influence both Land
1397 Use/Zoning, which determines proximity to AFOs (and thereby exposure to odors), and
1398 Education Level, which could influence smoking habits and health outcomes like chronic
1399 bronchitis. Here, SES creates a bias pathway that needs to be controlled to correctly estimate
1400 the causal effect of odors on bronchitis. A confounder is also interpreted as a "backdoor path".
1401 In a DAG, a backdoor path is any non-causal pathway linking the exposure (X) and the outcome
1402 (Y). If we want to estimate the causal effect of X on Y, we need to "block" or "close" these paths.
1403 Blocking or closing a path means preventing the flow of association between X and Y that
1404 travels through confounders. This is typically done by *controlling for* or *adjusting for* the
1405 confounding variables, meaning they are included in the analysis as covariates to neutralize
1406 their impact on the exposure-outcome relationship. In the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, by

1407 controlling for Socioeconomic Status, we block the backdoor path and reduce the confounding
1408 bias.

1409
1410 •—AFO emissions (Odors (NH₃, H₂S)) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress
1411 → Smoking ← Education Level ← SES

1412 In the Brewer et al. (2017), smoking is a collider because it is influenced by both "Chronic
1413 Individual Stress" (a descendant of Odors) and "Education Level" (which influences Chronic
1414 Bronchitis). In the DAG, this is visually represented by two arrows pointing toward Smoking, one
1415 from Chronic Individual Stress and another from Education Level. If researchers mistakenly
1416 adjust for a collider, such as Smoking, this opens a previously blocked path, allowing
1417 associations to flow between variables that were otherwise unconnected, thereby introducing
1418 bias into the analysis. This phenomenon is known as collider bias. (Cole et al. 2010) [Click or
1419 tap here to enter text.](#) In this context, "opening a path" means creating an unintended link
1420 between variables by controlling for a collider, which allows spurious associations to distort the
1421 causal inference.

1422
1423 •—AFO emissions (Odors (NH₃, H₂S)) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress
1424 → Smoking → Chronic Bronchitis

1425 In the Brewer et al. (2017), perception of Health Risk is a mediator because it lies on the causal
1426 pathway between the exposure and the outcome. Controlling for this variable would block part
1427 of the causal pathway and prevent the full impact of odors on bronchitis from being observed,
1428 resulting in an underestimated total effect. While controlling for mediators can help estimate the
1429 direct effect of an exposure on an outcome, it blocks the pathway through which the exposure
1430 impacts the outcome indirectly, thus reducing the total effect to the direct effect only (Tennant et
1431 al. 2021). Controlling a mediator variable is not an error if only the direct effect is of interest.
1432 However, this should be conveyed to the end users of the research. If the total effect (direct and
1433 indirect pathways) is of interest, then researchers would want to avoid controlling for mediators.
1434 Understanding of mediation and the control of intermediate variables offers valuable
1435 perspectives on estimating the target causal effect, whether it be the direct or total effect of
1436 exposure on the outcome. Total effect refers to the overall impact of an exposure (X) on an
1437 outcome (Y), including both direct and indirect effects. For instance, researchers can perform
1438 mediation analysis to assess how much of the effect of Odors on Chronic Bronchitis is mediated
1439 through pathways like Stress and Lung Inflammation, and how much is direct.

1440 A minimum sufficient adjustment set is the smallest group of variables that, when controlled for,
1441 effectively blocks all non-causal (backdoor) paths between the exposure and outcome while
1442 preserving the causal pathways. To identify this set, the first step is to examine all possible
1443 paths connecting the exposure (e.g., Odors) to the outcome (e.g., Chronic Bronchitis) in the
1444 DAG, including both causal and non-causal (backdoor) paths. The aim is to pinpoint the minimal
1445 set of variables that, when adjusted for, closes the backdoor paths (which are confounders)
1446 without inadvertently opening collider paths, thus allowing the causal relationship to remain
1447 unblocked. Finally, the proposed adjustment set should be tested to ensure it successfully
1448 blocks all confounding while leaving the causal path intact, often through statistical modeling or
1449 causal tools like DAGitty. It is not usual for multiple minimum sufficient adjustment sets to exist
1450 as in the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG. This can offer researchers different options for control
1451 variables which may have different feasibility. Further, the set may actually refer to a single
1452 variable as is the example in minimum sufficient adjustment set 1 and 2.

1453 According to the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, there exist two minimally sufficient adjustment sets
1454 for the estimation of the total causal effect of AFO exposure on the lower respiratory disease
1455 outcome, Chronic Bronchitis. These sets contain either:

- 1456 • Minimum sufficient adjustment set 1: Education Level
- 1457 • Minimum sufficient adjustment set 2: Land Use/ Zoning

1458 If the variable AFO is unobserved (and therefore cannot be controlled as proposed by (Brewer
1459 et al. 2017) then either Land use / Zoning or Education should be controlled to obtain an
1460 unbiased estimate of the total causal effect.

1461 **Brewer et al 2017 DAGitty code**
1462
1463 dag {
1464 bb="0,0,1,1"
1465 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.581,0.340"]
1466 "Chronic Bronchitis" [outcome,pos="0.965,0.369"]
1467 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
1468 "Education Level" [pos="0.171,0.564"]
1469 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.851,0.400"]
1470 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.595,0.436"]
1471 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
1472 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.729,0.413"]
1473 "Odors (NH3, H2S)" [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
1474 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]
1475 "Socioeconomic Status" [latent,pos="0.050,0.500"]
1476 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
1477 Smoking [pos="0.669,0.648"]
1478 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1479 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
1480 "Chronic Stress" -> Smoking
1481 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
1482 "Education Level" -> Smoking
1483 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis"
1484 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"

1485 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO

1486 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"

1487 "Odors (NH3, H2S)" -> "Bronchial Irritation"

1488 "Odors (NH3, H2S)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis"

1489 "Odors (NH3, H2S)" -> "Perceived Health Risk"

1490 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"

1491 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level"

1492 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"

1493 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S)"

1494 Smoking -> "Chronic Bronchitis"

1495 Smoking -> "Lung Inflammation"

1496 }

1497 **DAGitty code for mapping Radon et al. (2005) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG**

1498

1499 dag {

1500 bb="0,0,1,1"

1501 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]

1502 "Chronic Bronchitis (Non-Cold Related Rhonchal Breathing Sounds) "

1503 [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]

1504 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]

1505 "Education Level (Higher Education Status)" [adjusted,pos="0.195,0.548"]

1506 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]

1507 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

1508 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]

1509 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]

1510 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)"

1511 [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]

1512 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]

1513 "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status, Smoker Status)" [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]
1514 "Socioeconomic Status" [latent,pos="0.062,0.496"]
1515 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
1516 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1517 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
1518 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status, Smoker Status)"
1519 "Education Level (Higher Education Status)" -> "Chronic Stress"
1520 "Education Level (Higher Education Status)" -> "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status,
1521 Smoker Status)"
1522 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Non-Cold Related Rhonchal Breathing Sounds) "
1523 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1524 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
1525 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
1526 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)" -> "Bronchial
1527 Irritation"
1528 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)" -> "Chronic
1529 Bronchitis (Non-Cold Related Rhonchal Breathing Sounds) "
1530 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)" -> "Perceived
1531 Health Risk"
1532 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
1533 "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status, Smoker Status)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Non-Cold
1534 Related Rhonchal Breathing Sounds) "
1535 "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status, Smoker Status)" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1536 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level (Higher Education Status)"
1537 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"
1538 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)"
1539 }

1540 DAGitty code for mapping Mirabelli et al. (2006) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)
1541 DAG
1542
1543 dag {
1544 bb="0,0,1,1"
1545 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]
1546 "Chronic Bronchitis (Missed School Last Year as Result of Asthma)"
1547 [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]
1548 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
1549 "Education Level" [pos="0.195,0.548"]
1550 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]
1551 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]
1552 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
1553 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]
1554 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)" [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
1555 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]
1556 "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home)"
1557 [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]
1558 "Socioeconomic Status (Economic Status)" [adjusted,pos="0.099,0.479"]
1559 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
1560 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1561 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
1562 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home)"
1563 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
1564 "Education Level" -> "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home)"
1565 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Missed School Last Year as Result of Asthma)"
1566 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1567 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
1568 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
1569 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)" -> "Bronchial Irritation"

1570 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Missed School Last Year as
1571 Result of Asthma)"

1572 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)" -> "Perceived Health Risk"

1573 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"

1574 "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home) " -> "Chronic Bronchitis
1575 (Missed School Last Year as Result of Asthma)"

1576 "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home) " -> "Lung
1577 Inflammation"

1578 "Socioeconomic Status (Economic Status)" -> "Education Level"

1579 "Socioeconomic Status (Economic Status)" -> "Land use/Zoning"

1580 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)"

1581 }

1582 **DAGitty code for mapping Hoopmann et al. (2006) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)**
1583 **DAG**

1584

1585 dag {

1586 bb="0,0,1,1"

1587 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]

1588 "Chronic Bronchitis (Allergic Asthma) " [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]

1589 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]

1590 "Education Level" [adjusted,pos="0.195,0.548"]

1591 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]

1592 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

1593 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]

1594 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]

1595 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)" [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]

1596 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]

1597 "Smoking (Actual Smoking) " [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]

1598 "Socioeconomic Status" [pos="0.073,0.483"]

1599 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]

1600 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"

```

1601 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
1602 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Actual Smoking) "
1603 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
1604 "Education Level" -> "Smoking (Actual Smoking) "
1605 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Allergic Asthma) "
1606 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1607 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
1608 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
1609 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)" -> "Bronchial Irritation"
1610 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Allergic Asthma) "
1611 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)" -> "Perceived Health Risk"
1612 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
1613 "Smoking (Actual Smoking) " -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Allergic Asthma) "
1614 "Smoking (Actual Smoking) " -> "Lung Inflammation"
1615 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level"
1616 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"
1617 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)"
1618 }
1619
1620 DAGitty code for mapping Hooiveld et al. (2016) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)
1621 DAG
1622
1623 dag {
1624 bb="0,0,1,1"
1625 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]
1626 "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia **)" [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]
1627 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
1628 "Education Level" [pos="0.195,0.548"]
1629 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]
1630 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

```

1631 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
1632 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]
1633 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the residence)"
1634 [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
1635 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]
1636 "Socioeconomic Status" [pos="0.073,0.483"]
1637 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
1638 Smoking [pos="0.566,0.611"]
1639 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1640 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
1641 "Chronic Stress" -> Smoking
1642 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
1643 "Education Level" -> Smoking
1644 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia **)"
1645 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1646 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
1647 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
1648 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the residence)" ->
1649 "Bronchial Irritation"
1650 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the residence)" ->
1651 "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia **)"
1652 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the residence)" ->
1653 "Perceived Health Risk"
1654 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
1655 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level"
1656 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"
1657 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the
1658 residence)"
1659 Smoking -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia **)"
1660 Smoking -> "Lung Inflammation"
1661 }
1662

1663 DAGitty code for mapping Freidl et al. (2017) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG

1664

1665 dag {

1666 bb="0,0,1,1"

1667 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]

1668 "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia)" [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]

1669 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]

1670 "Education Level" [pos="0.195,0.548"]

1671 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]

1672 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

1673 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]

1674 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]

1675 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m of residence **)" [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]

1677 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]

1678 "Socioeconomic Status" [pos="0.073,0.483"]

1679 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]

1680 Smoking [pos="0.566,0.611"]

1681 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"

1682 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"

1683 "Chronic Stress" -> Smoking

1684 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"

1685 "Education Level" -> Smoking

1686 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia)" "

1687 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"

1688 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO

1689 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"

1690 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m of residence **)" -> "Bronchial Irritation"

1692 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m of residence **)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia)" "

1693

1694 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m of
1695 residence **)" -> "Perceived Health Risk"
1696 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
1697 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level"
1698 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"
1699 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m
1700 of residence **)"
1701 Smoking -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia) "
1702 Smoking -> "Lung Inflammation"
1703 }
1704 **DAGitty code for mapping Rasmussen et al. (2017) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)**
1705 **DAG**
1706
1707 dag {
1708 bb="0,0,1,1"
1709 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]
1710 "Chronic Bronchitis (Asthma hospitalizations **)" [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]
1711 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
1712 "Education Level" [pos="0.195,0.548"]
1713 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]
1714 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]
1715 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
1716 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]
1717 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO) "
1718 [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
1719 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]
1720 "SES (Community socioeconomic deprivation)" [adjusted,pos="0.109,0.461"]
1721 "Smoking (Smoking status)" [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]
1722 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
1723 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1724 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"

```

1725 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Smoking status)"
1726 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
1727 "Education Level" -> "Smoking (Smoking status)"
1728 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Asthma hospitalizations **)"
1729 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1730 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
1731 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
1732 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO)" ->
1733 "Bronchial Irritation"
1734 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO)" ->
1735 "Chronic Bronchitis (Asthma hospitalizations **)"
1736 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO)" ->
1737 "Perceived Health Risk"
1738 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
1739 "SES (Community socioeconomic deprivation)" -> "Education Level"
1740 "SES (Community socioeconomic deprivation)" -> "Land use/Zoning"
1741 "Smoking (Smoking status)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Asthma hospitalizations **)"
1742 "Smoking (Smoking status)" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1743 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO)"
1744 "
1745 }"
1746 DAGitty code for mapping Schultz et al. (2019) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)
1747 DAG
1748
1749 dag {
1750 bb="0,0,1,1"
1751 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]
1752 "Chronic Bronchitis (Lung allergies **)" [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]
1753 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
1754 "Education Level" [adjusted,pos="0.195,0.548"]
1755 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]
1756 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

```

1757 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
1758 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]
1759 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest CAFO)"
1760 [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
1761 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]
1762 "SES (Poverty to income ratio)" [adjusted,pos="0.085,0.461"]
1763 "Smoking (Smoking status)" [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]
1764 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
1765 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1766 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
1767 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Smoking status)"
1768 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
1769 "Education Level" -> "Smoking (Smoking status)"
1770 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Lung allergies **)"
1771 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1772 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
1773 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
1774 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest CAFO)" ->
1775 "Bronchial Irritation"
1776 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest CAFO)" ->
1777 "Chronic Bronchitis (Lung allergies **)"
1778 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest CAFO)" ->
1779 "Perceived Health Risk"
1780 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
1781 "SES (Poverty to income ratio)" -> "Education Level"
1782 "SES (Poverty to income ratio)" -> "Land use/Zoning"
1783 "Smoking (Smoking status)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Lung allergies **)"
1784 "Smoking (Smoking status)" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1785 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest
1786 CAFO)"
1787 }

1788 Supplementary Table 1. Characteristics of relevant studies (listed chronologically from most
1789 recent) that provide estimates of the lower respiratory tract conditions.

<u>Study</u>	<u>Country</u>	<u>Study Design</u>
<u>(Schultz et al. 2019)</u>	<u>USA</u>	<u>Cross-sectional</u>
<u>(Freidl et al. 2017)</u>	<u>Netherlands</u>	<u>Cross-sectional</u>
<u>(Rasmussen et al. 2017)</u>	<u>USA</u>	<u>Case-Control</u>
<u>(Hooiveld et al. 2016)</u>	<u>Netherlands</u>	<u>Cohort</u>
<u>(Radon et al. 2007)</u>	<u>Germany</u>	<u>Cross-sectional</u>
<u>(Hoopmann et al. 2006)</u>	<u>Germany</u>	<u>Cross-sectional</u>
<u>(Mirabelli et al. 2006)</u>	<u>USA</u>	<u>Cross-sectional</u>
<u>(Radon et al. 2005)</u>	<u>Germany</u>	<u>Cross-sectional</u>

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1798 [Supplementary Figure 1. Literature flow diagram for the living systematic review on the effects of](#)
1799 [animal feeding operations \(AFOs\) on the health of people living nearby. The diagram illustrates](#)
1800 [the number of records identified, screened, assessed for eligibility, excluded and included in the](#)
1801 [review.](#)

1802

1803

```

1804 BREWER-ET-AL-2017-DAG-CODE
1805
1806 DAG {
1807 BB="0,0,1,1"
1808 "BROCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3 AND H2S" [LATENT,POS="0.202,0.247"]
1809 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS" [OUTCOME,POS="0.469,0.859"]
1810 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" [LATENT,POS="0.460,0.409"]
1811 "EDUCATION LEVEL" [POS="0.707,0.601"]
1812 "EXHALED NITRIC OXIDE (BIOMARKER)" [POS="0.305,0.703"]
1813 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" [LATENT,POS="0.351,0.493"]
1814 "LANDUSE/ ZONING" [POS="0.697,0.277"]
1815 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" [LATENT,POS="0.199,0.597"]
1816 "ODORS (NH3, H2S)" [EXPOSURE,POS="0.460,0.077"]
1817 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" [POS="0.459,0.282"]
1818 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS" [LATENT,POS="0.698,0.434"]
1819 CAFO [LATENT,POS="0.581,0.185"]
1820 SMOKING [POS="0.469,0.600"]
1821 "BROCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3 AND H2S" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
1822 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS" <-> SMOKING
1823 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION"
1824 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> SMOKING
1825 "EDUCATION LEVEL" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
1826 "EDUCATION LEVEL" -> SMOKING
1827 "EXHALED NITRIC OXIDE (BIOMARKER)" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS"
1828 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
1829 "LANDUSE/ ZONING" -> CAFO
1830 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" -> "EXHALED NITRIC OXIDE (BIOMARKER)"
1831 "ODORS (NH3, H2S)" -> "BROCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3 AND H2S"
1832 "ODORS (NH3, H2S)" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS" [POS="0.672,0.429"]
1833 "ODORS (NH3, H2S)" -> "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK"
1834 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
1835 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS" -> "EDUCATION LEVEL"
1836 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS" -> "LANDUSE/ ZONING" [POS="0.551,0.295"]
1837 CAFO -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S)"
1838 SMOKING -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
1839 }
1840
1841

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1844
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SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE 1. CHARACTERISTICS OF RELEVANT STUDIES (LISTED CHRONOLOGICALLY FROM MOST RECENT) THAT PROVIDE ESTIMATES OF THE LOWER RESPIRATORY TRACT CONDITIONS.

STUDY	COUNTRY	STUDY DESIGN
(SCHULTZ ET AL. 2019)	USA	CROSS-SECTIONAL
(FREIDL ET AL. 2017)	NETHERLANDS	CROSS-SECTIONAL
(RASMUSSEN ET AL. 2017)	USA	CASE-CONTROL
(HOOIVELD ET AL. 2016)	NETHERLANDS	COHORT
(RADON ET AL. 2007)	GERMANY	CROSS-SECTIONAL
(HOOPMANN ET AL. 2006)	GERMANY	CROSS-SECTIONAL
(MIRABELLI ET AL. 2006)	USA	CROSS-SECTIONAL
(RADON ET AL. 2005)	GERMANY	CROSS-SECTIONAL

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DAGS PROPOSED FOR EXPOSURE-OUTCOME PAIRS IN RADON ET AL. 2005; MIRABELLI ET AL. 2006; HOOPMANN ET AL. 2006; RADON ET AL. 2007; HOOIVELD ET AL. 2016; FREIDL ET AL. 2017; RASMUSSEN ET AL. 2017; SCHULTZ ET AL. 2019

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SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 1. DAG GENERATED FOR RADON ET AL 2005 USING DAGITTY.NET. THE DAG ALLOWS VARIABLES TO BE LABELED AS EXPOSURE VARIABLES (GREEN CIRCLE WITH INNER TRIANGLE), OUTCOME (BLUE CIRCLE WITH INNER "I"), CONFOUNDERS (RED LIGHT CIRCLE), AND ADJUSTED VARIABLES (ILLUSTRATED BY A WHITE CIRCLE NODE). GREEN ARROWS REPRESENT UNBIASED CAUSAL PATHS AND

1862 RED ARROWS INDICATED BIASING PATHS. THE MODEL CODE IS LISTED BELOW. ABBREVIATIONS: NH3 =
1863 AMMONIA; H2S = HYDROGEN SULFIDE.
1864
1865 **DAGITY CODE FOR** GENERATING FOR RADON ET AL 2005 USING DAGITY.NET.
1866 DAG {
1867 BB="0,0,1,1"
1868 "ALLERGIES OF PARENTS" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.902,0.212"]
1869 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" [LATENT,POS="0.202,0.247"]
1870 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (NON-COLD RELATED RHONCHAL BREATHING SOUNDS)"
1871 [OUTCOME,POS="0.459,0.891"]
1872 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" [LATENT,POS="0.460,0.409"]
1873 "EDUCATION LEVEL (HIGHER EDUCATION STATUS)" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.707,0.601"]
1874 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" [LATENT,POS="0.327,0.497"]
1875 "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.707,0.267"]
1876 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" [LATENT,POS="0.199,0.597"]
1877 "NUMBER OF SIBLINGS" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.090,0.161"]
1878 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500M, LEVEL OF ODOR ANNOYANCE)"
1879 [EXPOSURE,POS="0.460,0.077"]
1880 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" [POS="0.459,0.282"]
1881 "SMOKING (SECOND-HAND SMOKE EXPOSURE, SMOKER-STATUS)"
1882 [ADJUSTED,POS="0.458,0.668"]
1883 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " [POS="0.703,0.438"]
1884 AGE [ADJUSTED,POS="0.061,0.489"]
1885 CAFO [LATENT,POS="0.598,0.189"]
1886 GENDER [ADJUSTED,POS="0.876,0.067"]
1887 "ALLERGIES OF PARENTS" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (NON-COLD RELATED RHONCHAL
1888 BREATHING SOUNDS)"
1889 "ALLERGIES OF PARENTS" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500M, LEVEL
1890 OF ODOR ANNOYANCE)"
1891 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
1892 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION"
1893 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "SMOKING (SECOND-HAND SMOKE EXPOSURE,
1894 SMOKER-STATUS)" [POS="0.459,0.571"]
1895 "EDUCATION LEVEL (HIGHER EDUCATION STATUS)" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
1896 "EDUCATION LEVEL (HIGHER EDUCATION STATUS)" -> "SMOKING (SECOND-HAND
1897 SMOKE EXPOSURE, SMOKER-STATUS)"
1898 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
1899 "LAND USE/ ZONING" -> CAFO
1900 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (NON-COLD RELATED RHONCHAL
1901 BREATHING SOUNDS)"
1902 "NUMBER OF SIBLINGS" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (NON-COLD RELATED RHONCHAL
1903 BREATHING SOUNDS)"
1904 "NUMBER OF SIBLINGS" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500M, LEVEL
1905 OF ODOR ANNOYANCE)"
1906 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500M, LEVEL OF ODOR ANNOYANCE)" ->
1907 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S"
1908 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500M, LEVEL OF ODOR ANNOYANCE)" ->
1909 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK"
1910 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
1911 "SMOKING (SECOND-HAND SMOKE EXPOSURE, SMOKER-STATUS)" -> "CHRONIC
1912 BRONCHITIS (NON-COLD RELATED RHONCHAL BREATHING SOUNDS)"

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1913 "SMOKING (SECOND-HAND SMOKE EXPOSURE, SMOKER-STATUS)" -> "LUNG
1914 INFLAMMATION"
1915 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "EDUCATION LEVEL (HIGHER EDUCATION STATUS)"
1916 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.612,0.287"]
1917 AGE -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (NON-COLD RELATED RHONCHAL BREATHING
1918 SOUNDS)"
1919 AGE -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500M, LEVEL OF ODOR
1920 ANNOYANCE)"
1921 CAFO -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500M, LEVEL OF ODOR
1922 ANNOYANCE)"
1923 GENDER -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (NON-COLD RELATED RHONCHAL BREATHING
1924 SOUNDS)"
1925 GENDER -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500M, LEVEL OF ODOR
1926 ANNOYANCE)"
1927 }
1928
```


1930
 1931 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 2. DAG GENERATED FOR MIRABELLI ET AL., 2006 USING DAGITTY.NET. THE DAG
 1932 ALLOWS VARIABLES TO BE LABELED AS EXPOSURE VARIABLES (GREEN CIRCLE WITH INNER TRIANGLE),
 1933 OUTCOME (BLUE CIRCLE WITH INNER "I"), CONFOUNDERS (RED LIGHT CIRCLE), AND ADJUSTED VARIABLES
 1934 (ILLUSTRATED BY A WHITE CIRCLE NODE). GREEN ARROWS REPRESENT UNBIASED CAUSAL PATHS AND
 1935 RED ARROWS INDICATED BIASING PATHS. ** OTHER OUTCOMES ASSESSED FOR THIS EXPOSURE ARE
 1936 LISTED BELOW, AS WELL AS THE MODEL CODE. ABBREVIATIONS: NH3 – AMMONIA; H2S – HYDROGEN
 1937 SULFIDE.

1938
 1939 **OTHER OUTCOMES:** ASTHMA-RELATED PHYSICIAN VISIT EMERGENCY VISIT AND/OR
 1940 HOSPITALIZATION IN PAST YEAR, SELF-REPORTED ALLERGIES, ASTHMA-RELATED
 1941 PHYSICIAN VISIT EMERGENCY VISIT AND/OR HOSPITALIZATION IN PAST YEAR ALL

1942 CHILDREN, ASTHMA-RELATED PHYSICIAN VISIT—EMERGENCY VISIT AND/OR
1943 HOSPITALIZATION IN THE PAST YEAR SELF-REPORTED ALLERGIES.
1944
1945 **DAGITTY CODE:**
1946 DAG {
1947 BB="0,0,1,1"
1948 "ALLERGY STATUS" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.575,0.782"]
1949 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" [LATENT,POS="0.204,0.214"]
1950 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (MISSED SCHOOL LAST YEAR AS A RESULT OF ASTHMA **)"
1951 [OUTCOME,POS="0.455,0.863"]
1952 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" [LATENT,POS="0.460,0.409"]
1953 "EDUCATION LEVEL" [POS="0.707,0.601"]
1954 "HISPANIC ETHNICITY" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.148,0.828"]
1955 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" [LATENT,POS="0.327,0.497"]
1956 "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.707,0.267"]
1957 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" [LATENT,POS="0.204,0.624"]
1958 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LIVESTOCK ODOR REPORTED INSIDE AND OUTSIDE THE SCHOOL
1959 BUILDING)" [EXPOSURE,POS="0.460,0.077"]
1960 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" [POS="0.459,0.282"]
1961 "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS, EXPOSURE TO SECONDHAND SMOKE AT HOME)"
1962 [ADJUSTED,POS="0.458,0.668"]
1963 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (ECONOMIC STATUS)" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.703,0.438"]
1964 "USE OF GAS STOVE" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.807,0.906"]
1965 AGE [ADJUSTED,POS="0.347,0.827"]
1966 CAFO [LATENT,POS="0.598,0.189"]
1967 GENDER [ADJUSTED,POS="0.698,0.791"]
1968 RACE [POS="0.598,0.392"]
1969 "ALLERGY STATUS" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (MISSED SCHOOL LAST YEAR AS A
1970 RESULT OF ASTHMA **)"
1971 "ALLERGY STATUS" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LIVESTOCK ODOR REPORTED INSIDE AND
1972 OUTSIDE THE SCHOOL BUILDING)"
1973 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
1974 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (MISSED SCHOOL LAST YEAR AS A RESULT OF ASTHMA **)" <->
1975 "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS, EXPOSURE TO SECONDHAND SMOKE AT HOME)"
1976 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION"
1977 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS, EXPOSURE TO
1978 SECONDHAND SMOKE AT HOME)" [POS="0.459,0.571"]
1979 "EDUCATION LEVEL" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
1980 "EDUCATION LEVEL" -> "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS, EXPOSURE TO SECONDHAND
1981 SMOKE AT HOME)"
1982 "HISPANIC ETHNICITY" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (MISSED SCHOOL LAST YEAR AS A
1983 RESULT OF ASTHMA **)"
1984 "HISPANIC ETHNICITY" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LIVESTOCK ODOR REPORTED INSIDE
1985 AND OUTSIDE THE SCHOOL BUILDING)"
1986 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
1987 "LAND USE/ ZONING" -> CAFO
1988 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (MISSED SCHOOL LAST YEAR AS A
1989 RESULT OF ASTHMA **)"
1990 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LIVESTOCK ODOR REPORTED INSIDE AND OUTSIDE THE SCHOOL
1991 BUILDING)" -> "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S"

1992 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LIVESTOCK ODOR REPORTED INSIDE AND OUTSIDE THE SCHOOL
1993 BUILDING)" -> "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK"
1994 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" -> "CHRONIC INDIVIDUAL STRESS"
1995 "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS, EXPOSURE TO SECONDHAND SMOKE AT HOME)" ->
1996 "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
1997 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (ECONOMIC STATUS)" -> "EDUCATION LEVEL"
1998 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (ECONOMIC STATUS)" -> "LAND USE/ZONING"
1999 [POS="0.612,0.287"]
2000 "USE OF GAS STOVE" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (MISSED SCHOOL LAST YEAR AS A
2001 RESULT OF ASTHMA **)"
2002 "USE OF GAS STOVE" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LIVESTOCK ODOR REPORTED INSIDE AND
2003 OUTSIDE THE SCHOOL BUILDING)"
2004 AGE -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (MISSED SCHOOL LAST YEAR AS A RESULT OF ASTHMA
2005 **)"
2006 AGE -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LIVESTOCK ODOR REPORTED INSIDE AND OUTSIDE THE
2007 SCHOOL BUILDING)"
2008 CAFO -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LIVESTOCK ODOR REPORTED INSIDE AND OUTSIDE THE
2009 SCHOOL BUILDING)"
2010 GENDER -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (MISSED SCHOOL LAST YEAR AS A RESULT OF
2011 ASTHMA **)"
2012 GENDER -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LIVESTOCK ODOR REPORTED INSIDE AND OUTSIDE
2013 THE SCHOOL BUILDING)"
2014 RACE -> "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (ECONOMIC STATUS)"
2015 }
2016 }

2018
 2019
 2020
 2021
 2022
 2023
 2024
 2025
 2026
 2027
 2028
 2029

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 3. DAG GENERATED FOR HOOPMANN ET AL 2006 USING DAGITTY.NET. NODES THAT ARE "UPSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE KNOWN AS ANCESTORS AND NODES THAT ARE "DOWNSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE DECEDENTS. THE DAG ALLOWS VARIABLES TO BE LABELED AS EXPOSURE VARIABLES (GREEN CIRCLE WITH INNER TRIANGLE), OUTCOME (BLUE CIRCLE WITH INNER "I"), CONFOUNDERS (RED LIGHT CIRCLE), AND ADJUSTED VARIABLES (ILLUSTRATED BY A WHITE CIRCLE NODE). GREEN ARROWS REPRESENT UNBIASED CAUSAL PATHS AND RED ARROWS INDICATED BIASING PATHS. ** OTHER OUTCOMES ASSESSED FOR THIS EXPOSURE ARE LISTED BELOW, AS WELL AS THE MODEL CODE. ABBREVIATIONS: NH3 = AMMONIA; H2S = HYDROGEN SULFIDE.

OTHER OUTCOMES: ALLERGIC ASTHMA-ATOPIC PARENTS, NON-ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-ATOPIC PARENTS, NON-ALLERGIC ASTHMA-ATOPIC PARENTS, ASTHMATIC

2030 PATHOLOGY NOT ATOPIC PARENTS, ASTHMATIC PATHOLOGY ATOPIC PARENTS,
 2031 ASTHMATIC PATHOLOGY, IGE.
 2032
 2033 **DAGITTY CODE:**
 2034 DAG {
 2035 BB="0,0,1,1"
 2036 "BREASTFED AT LEAST 4 MONTHS" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.178,0.725"]
 2037 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" [LATENT,POS="0.202,0.247"]
 2038 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-ATOPIC PARENTS **)"
 2039 [OUTCOME,POS="0.459,0.891"]
 2040 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" [LATENT,POS="0.460,0.409"]
 2041 "CONTACT WITH CATS AT A YOUNG AGE" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.839,0.933"]
 2042 "EDUCATION LEVEL " [ADJUSTED,POS="0.707,0.601"]
 2043 "EXPERIENCED STREET NOISE" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.716,0.741"]
 2044 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" [LATENT,POS="0.327,0.497"]
 2045 "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.707,0.267"]
 2046 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" [LATENT,POS="0.199,0.597"]
 2047 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)" [EXPOSURE,POS="0.460,0.077"]
 2048 "OLDEST SIBLING" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.634,0.850"]
 2049 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" [POS="0.459,0.282"]
 2050 "RUG/CARPETED FLOOR" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.214,0.836"]
 2051 "SMOKING (ACTUAL SMOKING)" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.458,0.668"]
 2052 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " [POS="0.703,0.438"]
 2053 CAFO [LATENT,POS="0.598,0.189"]
 2054 GENDER [ADJUSTED,POS="0.348,0.850"]
 2055 MOLD [ADJUSTED,POS="0.554,0.809"]
 2056 "BREASTFED AT LEAST 4 MONTHS" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-
 2057 ATOPIC PARENTS **)"
 2058 "BREASTFED AT LEAST 4 MONTHS" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)"
 2059 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
 2060 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION"
 2061 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "SMOKING (ACTUAL SMOKING)" [POS="0.459,0.571"]
 2062 "CONTACT WITH CATS AT A YOUNG AGE" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC
 2063 ASTHMA-NON-ATOPIC PARENTS **)"
 2064 "CONTACT WITH CATS AT A YOUNG AGE" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE
 2065 ENDOTOXIN)"
 2066 "EDUCATION LEVEL " -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
 2067 "EDUCATION LEVEL " -> "SMOKING (ACTUAL SMOKING)"
 2068 "EXPERIENCED STREET NOISE" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-
 2069 ATOPIC PARENTS **)"
 2070 "EXPERIENCED STREET NOISE" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)"
 2071 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
 2072 "LAND USE/ ZONING" -> CAFO
 2073 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-ATOPIC
 2074 PARENTS **)"
 2075 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)" -> "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3,
 2076 H2S"
 2077 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)" -> "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK"
 2078 "OLDEST SIBLING" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-ATOPIC
 2079 PARENTS **)"
 2080 "OLDEST SIBLING" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)"

2081 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" -> "CHRONIC INDIVIDUAL STRESS"
2082 "RUG/CARPETED FLOOR" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-ATOPIC
2083 PARENTS **)"
2084 "RUG/CARPETED FLOOR" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)"
2085 "SMOKING (ACTUAL SMOKING)" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-
2086 ATOPIC PARENTS **)"
2087 "SMOKING (ACTUAL SMOKING)" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2088 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "EDUCATION LEVEL "
2089 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.612,0.287"]
2090 CAFO -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)"
2091 GENDER -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-ATOPIC PARENTS **)"
2092 GENDER -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)"
2093 MOLD -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ALLERGIC ASTHMA-NON-ATOPIC PARENTS **)"
2094 MOLD -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (LOG OF THE ENDOTOXIN)"
2095 }
2096 }

2097
2098

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2102
2103
2104
2105

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 4. DAG GENERATED FOR RADON ET AL 2007 USING DAGITTY.NET. NODES THAT ARE "UPSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE KNOWN AS ANCESTORS AND NODES THAT ARE "DOWNSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE DECEDENTS. THE DAG ALLOWS VARIABLES TO BE LABELED AS EXPOSURE VARIABLES (GREEN CIRCLE WITH INNER TRIANGLE), OUTCOME (BLUE CIRCLE WITH INNER "I"), CONFOUNDERS (RED LIGHT CIRCLE), AND ADJUSTED VARIABLES (ILLUSTRATED BY A WHITE CIRCLE NODE). GREEN ARROWS REPRESENT UNBIASED CAUSAL PATHS AND RED ARROWS INDICATED

2|106 BIASING PATHS. ** OTHER OUTCOMES ASSESSED FOR THIS EXPOSURE ARE LISTED BELOW, AS WELL AS
2|107 THE MODEL CODE. ABBREVIATIONS: NH3 = AMMONIA; H2S = HYDROGEN SULFIDE.
2|108
2|109 **OTHER OUTCOMES:** BRONCHIAL HYPERRESPONSIVENESS TO METHACHOLINE,
2|110 PHYSICIAN-DIAGNOSED ASTHMA.
2|111 **DAGITTY CODE:**
2|112 DAG-{
2|113 BB="0,0,1,1"
2|114 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" [LATENT,POS="0.202,0.247"]
2|115 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (WHEEZING WITHOUT COLD **)" [OUTCOME,POS="0.459,0.891"]
2|116 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" [LATENT,POS="0.460,0.409"]
2|117 "EDUCATION LEVEL (LEVE OF EDUCATION)" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.707,0.601"]
2|118 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" [LATENT,POS="0.327,0.497"]
2|119 "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.707,0.267"]
2|120 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" [LATENT,POS="0.199,0.597"]
2|121 "NUMBER OF SIBLINGS" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.089,0.182"]
2|122 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (NO. OF ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500 M, LEVEL OF ODOR
2|123 ANNOYANCE)" [EXPOSURE,POS="0.460,0.077"]
2|124 "PARENTAL ALLERGIES " [ADJUSTED,POS="0.902,0.212"]
2|125 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" [POS="0.459,0.282"]
2|126 "SMOKING (ACTIVE AND PASSIVE SMOKE EXPOSURE)" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.458,0.668"]
2|127 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " [POS="0.703,0.438"]
2|128 AGE [ADJUSTED,POS="0.072,0.546"]
2|129 CAFO [LATENT,POS="0.598,0.189"]
2|130 SEX [ADJUSTED,POS="0.876,0.067"]
2|131 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2|132 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION"
2|133 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "SMOKING (ACTIVE AND PASSIVE SMOKE
2|134 EXPOSURE)" [POS="0.459,0.571"]
2|135 "EDUCATION LEVEL (LEVE OF EDUCATION)" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
2|136 "EDUCATION LEVEL (LEVE OF EDUCATION)" -> "SMOKING (ACTIVE AND PASSIVE SMOKE
2|137 EXPOSURE)"
2|138 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2|139 "LAND USE/ ZONING" -> CAFO
2|140 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (WHEEZING WITHOUT COLD **)"
2|141 "NUMBER OF SIBLINGS" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (WHEEZING WITHOUT COLD **)"
2|142 "NUMBER OF SIBLINGS" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (NO. OF ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500 M,
2|143 LEVEL OF ODOR ANNOYANCE)"
2|144 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (NO. OF ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500 M, LEVEL OF ODOR
2|145 ANNOYANCE)" -> "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S"
2|146 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (NO. OF ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500 M, LEVEL OF ODOR
2|147 ANNOYANCE)" -> "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK"
2|148 "PARENTAL ALLERGIES " -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (WHEEZING WITHOUT COLD **)"
2|149 "PARENTAL ALLERGIES " -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (NO. OF ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500 M,
2|150 LEVEL OF ODOR ANNOYANCE)"
2|151 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
2|152 "SMOKING (ACTIVE AND PASSIVE SMOKE EXPOSURE)" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS
2|153 (WHEEZING WITHOUT COLD **)"
2|154 "SMOKING (ACTIVE AND PASSIVE SMOKE EXPOSURE)" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2|155 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "EDUCATION LEVEL (LEVE OF EDUCATION)"
2|156 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.612,0.287"]

2|157 AGE->"CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (WHEEZING WITHOUT COLD **)"
2|158 AGE->"ODORS (NH3, H2S) (NO. OF ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500 M, LEVEL OF ODOR
2|159 ANNOYANCE)"
2|160 CAFO->"ODORS (NH3, H2S) (NO. OF ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500 M, LEVEL OF ODOR
2|161 ANNOYANCE)"
2|162 SEX->"CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (WHEEZING WITHOUT COLD **)"
2|163 SEX->"ODORS (NH3, H2S) (NO. OF ANIMAL HOUSES WITHIN 500 M, LEVEL OF ODOR
2|164 ANNOYANCE)"
2|165 }
2|166
2|167

2168
 2169 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 5. DAG GENERATED FOR HOOVELD ET AL 2016 USING DAGITTY.NET. NODES
 2170 THAT ARE "UPSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE KNOWN AS ANCESTORS AND NODES THAT
 2171 ARE "DOWNSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE DECEDEENTS. THE DAG ALLOWS VARIABLES TO
 2172 BE LABELED AS EXPOSURE VARIABLES (GREEN CIRCLE WITH INNER TRIANGLE), OUTCOME (BLUE CIRCLE
 2173 WITH INNER "I"), CONFOUNDERS (RED LIGHT CIRCLE), AND ADJUSTED VARIABLES (ILLUSTRATED BY A
 2174 WHITE CIRCLE NODE). GREEN ARROWS REPRESENT UNBIASED CAUSAL PATHS AND RED ARROWS

2175 INDICATED BIASING PATHS. ** OTHER OUTCOMES ASSESSED FOR THIS EXPOSURE ARE LISTED BELOW, AS
 2176 WELL AS THE MODEL CODE. ABBREVIATIONS: NH3 = AMMONIA; H2S = HYDROGEN SULFIDE.
 2177 ~~OTHER OUTCOMES:~~ PHYSICIAN-DIAGNOSED ASTHMA, CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE
 2178 PULMONARY DISEASE (COPD)
 2179 **DAGITTY CODE:**
 2180 DAG-{
 2181 BB="0,0,1,1"
 2182 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" [LATENT,POS="0.202,0.247"]
 2183 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA **)" [OUTCOME,POS="0.459,0.865"]
 2184 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" [LATENT,POS="0.460,0.409"]
 2185 "EDUCATION LEVEL " [POS="0.707,0.601"]
 2186 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" [LATENT,POS="0.327,0.497"]
 2187 "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.707,0.267"]
 2188 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" [LATENT,POS="0.199,0.597"]
 2189 "NUMBER OF INHABITANTS IN THE POSTAL CODE AREA AND TOTAL SURFACE AREA"
 2190 [ADJUSTED,POS="0.675,0.914"]
 2191 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (EACH ADDITIONAL CAFO WITHIN THE POSTAL CODE AREA OF THE
 2192 RESIDENCE)" [EXPOSURE,POS="0.460,0.077"]
 2193 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" [POS="0.459,0.282"]
 2194 "REGISTRY DURATION" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.298,0.774"]
 2195 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " [POS="0.703,0.438"]
 2196 AGE [ADJUSTED,POS="0.564,0.788"]
 2197 CAFO [LATENT,POS="0.598,0.189"]
 2198 GENDER [ADJUSTED,POS="0.707,0.788"]
 2199 SMOKING [POS="0.458,0.668"]
 2200 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
 2201 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION"
 2202 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> SMOKING [POS="0.459,0.571"]
 2203 "EDUCATION LEVEL " -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
 2204 "EDUCATION LEVEL " -> SMOKING
 2205 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
 2206 "LAND USE/ ZONING" -> CAFO
 2207 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA **)"
 2208 "NUMBER OF INHABITANTS IN THE POSTAL CODE AREA AND TOTAL SURFACE AREA" ->
 2209 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA **)"
 2210 "NUMBER OF INHABITANTS IN THE POSTAL CODE AREA AND TOTAL SURFACE AREA" ->
 2211 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (EACH ADDITIONAL CAFO WITHIN THE POSTAL CODE AREA OF THE
 2212 RESIDENCE)"
 2213 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (EACH ADDITIONAL CAFO WITHIN THE POSTAL CODE AREA OF THE
 2214 RESIDENCE)" -> "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S"
 2215 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (EACH ADDITIONAL CAFO WITHIN THE POSTAL CODE AREA OF THE
 2216 RESIDENCE)" -> "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK"
 2217 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
 2218 "REGISTRY DURATION" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA **)"
 2219 "REGISTRY DURATION" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (EACH ADDITIONAL CAFO WITHIN THE
 2220 POSTAL CODE AREA OF THE RESIDENCE)"
 2221 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "EDUCATION LEVEL "
 2222 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.612,0.287"]
 2223 AGE -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA **)"
 2224 AGE -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (EACH ADDITIONAL CAFO WITHIN THE POSTAL CODE AREA
 2225 OF THE RESIDENCE)"

2226 CAFO -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (EACH ADDITIONAL CAFO WITHIN THE POSTAL CODE AREA
2227 OF THE RESIDENCE)"
2228 GENDER -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA **)"
2229 GENDER -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (EACH ADDITIONAL CAFO WITHIN THE POSTAL CODE
2230 AREA OF THE RESIDENCE)"
2231 SMOKING -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA **)"
2232 SMOKING -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2233 }
2234
2235

2236 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 6. DAG GENERATED FOR FREIDL ET AL 2017 USING DAGITTY.NET. NODES THAT
 2237 ARE "UPSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE KNOWN AS ANCESTORS AND NODES THAT ARE
 2238 ARE "DOWNSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE DECEDEENTS. THE DAG ALLOWS VARIABLES TO BE
 2239 Labeled AS EXPOSURE VARIABLES (GREEN CIRCLE WITH INNER TRIANGLE), OUTCOME (BLUE CIRCLE WITH
 2240 INNER "I"), CONFOUNDERS (RED LIGHT CIRCLE), AND ADJUSTED VARIABLES (ILLUSTRATED BY A WHITE
 2241 CIRCLE NODE). GREEN ARROWS REPRESENT UNBIASED CAUSAL PATHS AND RED ARROWS INDICATED
 2242 BIASING PATHS. ** OTHER OUTCOMES ASSESSED FOR THIS EXPOSURE ARE LISTED BELOW, AS WELL AS
 2243 THE MODEL CODE. ABBREVIATIONS: NH3 = AMMONIA; H2S = HYDROGEN SULFIDE.

2245
 2246 **OTHER EXPOSURES:** PRESENCE OF FARM WITH MINIMUM AMOUNT OF ANIMALS
 2247 WITHIN 1000M OF RESIDENCE, PRESENCE OF FARM WITH MINIMUM AMOUNT OF
 2248 ANIMALS WITHIN 1500M OF RESIDENCE, PRESENCE OF FARM WITH MINIMUM AMOUNT
 2249 OF ANIMALS WITHIN 2000M OF RESIDENCE, DISTANCE (QUARTILES EXPRESSED IN
 2250 METERS) BETWEEN RESIDENCE AND CLOSEST FARM WITH MINIMUM 250 POULTRY,
 2251 DISTANCE (QUARTILES EXPRESSED IN METERS) BETWEEN RESIDENCE AND CLOSEST

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2252 FARM WITH MINIMUM 50 GOATS, NUMBER OF ANIMALS WITHIN 1000M OF THE
2253 RESIDENCE, NUMBER OF FARMS (ANY TYPE) WITHIN 1000M OF RESIDENCE.
2254 DAGITTY CODE:
2255 DAG {
2256 BB="0,0,1,1"
2257 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" [LATENT,POS="0.202,0.247"]
2258 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA)" [OUTCOME,POS="0.459,0.891"]
2259 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" [LATENT,POS="0.460,0.409"]
2260 "EDUCATION LEVEL " [POS="0.707,0.601"]
2261 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" [LATENT,POS="0.327,0.497"]
2262 "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.707,0.267"]
2263 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" [LATENT,POS="0.199,0.597"]
2264 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PRESENCE OF FARM WITH MINIMUM AMOUNT OF ANIMALS WITHIN
2265 500M OF RESIDENCE **)" [EXPOSURE,POS="0.460,0.077"]
2266 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" [POS="0.459,0.282"]
2267 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " [POS="0.703,0.438"]
2268 AGE [ADJUSTED,POS="0.691,0.803"]
2269 CAFO [LATENT,POS="0.598,0.189"]
2270 GENDER [ADJUSTED,POS="0.573,0.780"]
2271 SMOKING [POS="0.458,0.668"]
2272 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2273 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION"
2274 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> SMOKING [POS="0.459,0.571"]
2275 "EDUCATION LEVEL " -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
2276 "EDUCATION LEVEL " -> SMOKING
2277 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2278 "LAND USE/ ZONING" -> CAFO
2279 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA)"
2280 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PRESENCE OF FARM WITH MINIMUM AMOUNT OF ANIMALS WITHIN
2281 500M OF RESIDENCE **)" -> "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S"
2282 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PRESENCE OF FARM WITH MINIMUM AMOUNT OF ANIMALS WITHIN
2283 500M OF RESIDENCE **)" -> "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK"
2284 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
2285 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "EDUCATION LEVEL "
2286 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS " -> "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.612,0.287"]
2287 AGE -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA)"
2288 AGE -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PRESENCE OF FARM WITH MINIMUM AMOUNT OF ANIMALS
2289 WITHIN 500M OF RESIDENCE **)"
2290 CAFO -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PRESENCE OF FARM WITH MINIMUM AMOUNT OF ANIMALS
2291 WITHIN 500M OF RESIDENCE **)"
2292 GENDER -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA)"
2293 GENDER -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PRESENCE OF FARM WITH MINIMUM AMOUNT OF
2294 ANIMALS WITHIN 500M OF RESIDENCE **)"
2295 SMOKING -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (PNEUMONIA)"
2296 SMOKING -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2297 }
2298

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2299
 2300 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 7. DAG GENERATED FOR RASMUSSEN ET AL 2017 USING DAGITTY.NET. NODES
 2301 THAT ARE "UPSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE KNOWN AS ANCESTORS AND NODES THAT
 2302 ARE "DOWNSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE DECEDENTS. THE DAG ALLOWS VARIABLES TO
 2303 BE LABELED AS EXPOSURE VARIABLES (GREEN CIRCLE WITH INNER TRIANGLE), OUTCOME (BLUE CIRCLE
 2304 WITH INNER "I"), CONFOUNDERS (RED LIGHT CIRCLE), AND ADJUSTED VARIABLES (ILLUSTRATED BY A
 2305 WHITE CIRCLE NODE). GREEN ARROWS REPRESENT UNBIASED CAUSAL PATHS AND RED ARROWS

2306 INDICATED BIASING PATHS. ** OTHER OUTCOMES ASSESSED FOR THIS EXPOSURE ARE LISTED BELOW, AS
 2307 WELL AS THE MODEL CODE. ABBREVIATIONS: NH3 = AMMONIA; H2S = HYDROGEN SULFIDE.
 2308
 2309 **OTHER OUTCOMES:** ASTHMA EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT VISITS, NEW ASTHMA ORAL
 2310 CORTICOSTEROID ORDERS.
 2311 **DAGILITY CODE:**
 2312 DAG {
 2313 BB="0,0,1,1"
 2314 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" [LATENT,POS="0.202,0.247"]
 2315 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA HOSPITALIZATIONS **)" [OUTCOME,POS="0.455,0.863"]
 2316 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" [LATENT,POS="0.460,0.409"]
 2317 "DISTANCE TO ARTERIAL ROAD" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.738,0.928"]
 2318 "DISTANCE TO NEAREST HOSPITAL" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.649,0.823"]
 2319 "EDUCATION LEVEL" [POS="0.707,0.601"]
 2320 "FAMILY HISTORY OF ASTHMA" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.716,0.723"]
 2321 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" [LATENT,POS="0.327,0.497"]
 2322 "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.707,0.267"]
 2323 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" [LATENT,POS="0.200,0.593"]
 2324 "MEDICAL ASSISTANCE" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.215,0.806"]
 2325 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS TO NEAREST SWINE OR
 2326 CATTLE CAFO)" [EXPOSURE,POS="0.460,0.077"]
 2327 "OVERWEIGHT/OBESITY" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.126,0.905"]
 2328 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" [POS="0.459,0.282"]
 2329 "RACE/ETHNICITY " [ADJUSTED,POS="0.822,0.384"]
 2330 "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS)" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.458,0.668"]
 2331 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (COMMUNITY SOCIOECONOMIC DEPRIVATION)"
 2332 [ADJUSTED,POS="0.703,0.438"]
 2333 "TYPE 2 DIABETES" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.885,0.842"]
 2334 AGE [ADJUSTED,POS="0.339,0.827"]
 2335 CAFO [LATENT,POS="0.598,0.189"]
 2336 SEX [ADJUSTED,POS="0.293,0.750"]
 2337 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
 2338 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA HOSPITALIZATIONS **)" <-> "SMOKING (SMOKING
 2339 STATUS)"
 2340 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION"
 2341 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS)" [POS="0.459,0.571"]
 2342 "DISTANCE TO ARTERIAL ROAD" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA
 2343 HOSPITALIZATIONS **)"
 2344 "DISTANCE TO ARTERIAL ROAD" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL
 2345 ADDRESS TO NEAREST SWINE OR CATTLE CAFO)"
 2346 "DISTANCE TO NEAREST HOSPITAL" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA
 2347 HOSPITALIZATIONS **)"
 2348 "DISTANCE TO NEAREST HOSPITAL" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL
 2349 ADDRESS TO NEAREST SWINE OR CATTLE CAFO)"
 2350 "EDUCATION LEVEL" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
 2351 "EDUCATION LEVEL" -> "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS)"
 2352 "FAMILY HISTORY OF ASTHMA" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA HOSPITALIZATIONS
 2353 **)"
 2354 "FAMILY HISTORY OF ASTHMA" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL
 2355 ADDRESS TO NEAREST SWINE OR CATTLE CAFO)"
 2356 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"

2357 "LAND USE/ ZONING" -> CAFO
2358 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA HOSPITALIZATIONS **)"
2359 "MEDICAL ASSISTANCE" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA HOSPITALIZATIONS **)"
2360 "MEDICAL ASSISTANCE" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS
2361 TO NEAREST SWINE OR CATTLE CAFO)"
2362 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS TO NEAREST SWINE OR
2363 CATTLE CAFO)" -> "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S"
2364 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS TO NEAREST SWINE OR
2365 CATTLE CAFO)" -> "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK"
2366 "OVERWEIGHT/OBESITY" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA HOSPITALIZATIONS **)"
2367 "OVERWEIGHT/OBESITY" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS
2368 TO NEAREST SWINE OR CATTLE CAFO)"
2369 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" -> "CHRONIC INDIVIDUAL STRESS"
2370 "RACE/ETHNICITY" -> "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (COMMUNITY SOCIOECONOMIC
2371 DEPRIVATION)"
2372 "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS)" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2373 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (COMMUNITY SOCIOECONOMIC DEPRIVATION)" ->
2374 "EDUCATION LEVEL"
2375 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (COMMUNITY SOCIOECONOMIC DEPRIVATION)" -> "LAND
2376 USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.612,0.287"]
2377 "TYPE 2 DIABETES" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA HOSPITALIZATIONS **)"
2378 "TYPE 2 DIABETES" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS TO
2379 NEAREST SWINE OR CATTLE CAFO)"
2380 AGE -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA HOSPITALIZATIONS **)"
2381 AGE -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS TO NEAREST SWINE
2382 OR CATTLE CAFO)"
2383 CAFO -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS TO NEAREST
2384 SWINE OR CATTLE CAFO)"
2385 SEX -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (ASTHMA HOSPITALIZATIONS **)"
2386 SEX -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (PROXIMITY OF RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS TO NEAREST SWINE
2387 OR CATTLE CAFO)"
2388 }
2389 DAGS PROPOSED FOR EXPOSURE-OUTCOME PAIRS REPORTED IN SCHULTZ ET AL
2390 2019:

2391
 2392 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 8. DAG GENERATED FOR SCHULTZ ET AL 2019 USING DAGITTY.NET. NODES THAT
 2393 ARE "UPSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE KNOWN AS ANCESTORS AND NODES THAT ARE
 2394 "DOWNSTREAM" FROM A PARTICULAR VARIABLE ARE DECEDEENTS. THE DAG ALLOWS VARIABLES TO BE
 2395 LABELED AS EXPOSURE VARIABLES (GREEN CIRCLE WITH INNER TRIANGLE), OUTCOME (BLUE CIRCLE WITH
 2396 INNER "I"), CONFOUNDERS (RED LIGHT CIRCLE), AND ADJUSTED VARIABLES (ILLUSTRATED BY A WHITE
 2397 CIRCLE NODE). GREEN ARROWS REPRESENT UNBIASED CAUSAL PATHS AND RED ARROWS INDICATED

2398 BIASING PATHS. ** OTHER OUTCOMES ASSESSED FOR THIS EXPOSURE ARE LISTED BELOW, AS WELL AS
2399 THE MODEL CODE. ABBREVIATIONS: NH3 = AMMONIA; H2S = HYDROGEN SULFIDE.
2400
2401 **OTHER OUTCOMES:** NASAL OR LUNG ALLERGIES & CURRENT ASTHMA, CURRENT
2402 ASTHMA, ASTHMA (AT LEAST 1 EPISODE IN PAST YEAR), ASTHMA MEDICATION USE IN
2403 THE PAST YEAR, PHYSICIAN-DIAGNOSED ASTHMA.
2404 **DAGITYTY CODE:**
2405 DAG {
2406 BB="0,0,1,1"
2407 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" [LATENT,POS="0.202,0.247"]
2408 "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (LUNG ALLERGIES **)" [OUTCOME,POS="0.459,0.891"]
2409 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" [LATENT,POS="0.460,0.409"]
2410 "EDUCATION LEVEL " [ADJUSTED,POS="0.707,0.601"]
2411 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" [LATENT,POS="0.327,0.497"]
2412 "LAND USE/ ZONING" [POS="0.707,0.267"]
2413 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" [LATENT,POS="0.199,0.597"]
2414 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (RESTRICTED CUBIC SPLINE OF RESIDENTIAL DISTANCE TO THE
2415 NEAREST CAFO)" [EXPOSURE,POS="0.460,0.077"]
2416 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" [POS="0.459,0.282"]
2417 "PET OWNERSHIP" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.311,0.844"]
2418 "PROXIMITY TO MAJOR ROADWAYS" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.722,0.858"]
2419 "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS)" [ADJUSTED,POS="0.458,0.668"]
2420 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (POVERTY TO INCOME RATIO)"
2421 [ADJUSTED,POS="0.703,0.438"]
2422 AGE [ADJUSTED,POS="0.554,0.844"]
2423 BMI [ADJUSTED,POS="0.616,0.749"]
2424 CAFO [LATENT,POS="0.598,0.189"]
2425 GENDER [ADJUSTED,POS="0.216,0.764"]
2426 "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2427 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION"
2428 "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS" -> "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS)" [POS="0.459,0.571"]
2429 "EDUCATION LEVEL " -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
2430 "EDUCATION LEVEL " -> "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS)"
2431 "INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO INFECTION" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2432 "LAND USE/ ZONING" -> CAFO
2433 "LUNG INFLAMMATION" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (LUNG ALLERGIES **)"
2434 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (RESTRICTED CUBIC SPLINE OF RESIDENTIAL DISTANCE TO THE
2435 NEAREST CAFO)" -> "BRONCHIAL IRRITATION FROM NH3, H2S"
2436 "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (RESTRICTED CUBIC SPLINE OF RESIDENTIAL DISTANCE TO THE
2437 NEAREST CAFO)" -> "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK"
2438 "PERCEPTION OF HEALTH RISK" -> "CHRONIC LNDIVIDUAL STRESS"
2439 "PET OWNERSHIP" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (LUNG ALLERGIES **)"
2440 "PET OWNERSHIP" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (RESTRICTED CUBIC SPLINE OF RESIDENTIAL
2441 DISTANCE TO THE NEAREST CAFO)"
2442 "PROXIMITY TO MAJOR ROADWAYS" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (LUNG ALLERGIES **)"
2443 "PROXIMITY TO MAJOR ROADWAYS" -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (RESTRICTED CUBIC SPLINE
2444 OF RESIDENTIAL DISTANCE TO THE NEAREST CAFO)"
2445 "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS)" -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (LUNG ALLERGIES **)"
2446 "SMOKING (SMOKING STATUS)" -> "LUNG INFLAMMATION"
2447 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (POVERTY TO INCOME RATIO)" -> "EDUCATION LEVEL "

2448 "SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS (POVERTY TO INCOME RATIO)" -> "LAND USE/ ZONING"
 2449 [POS="0.612,0.287"]
 2450 AGE -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (LUNG ALLERGIES **)"
 2451 AGE -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (RESTRICTED CUBIC SPLINE OF RESIDENTIAL DISTANCE TO
 2452 THE NEAREST CAFO)"
 2453 BMI -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (LUNG ALLERGIES **)"
 2454 BMI -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (RESTRICTED CUBIC SPLINE OF RESIDENTIAL DISTANCE TO
 2455 THE NEAREST CAFO)"
 2456 CAFO -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (RESTRICTED CUBIC SPLINE OF RESIDENTIAL DISTANCE
 2457 TO THE NEAREST CAFO)"
 2458 GENDER -> "CHRONIC BRONCHITIS (LUNG ALLERGIES **)"
 2459 GENDER -> "ODORS (NH3, H2S) (RESTRICTED CUBIC SPLINE OF RESIDENTIAL
 2460 DISTANCE TO THE NEAREST CAFO)"
 2461 }
 2462

2463 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 9. LITERATURE FLOW DIAGRAM FOR THE LIVING SYSTEMATIC REVIEW ON THE
 2464 EFFECTS OF ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATIONS (AFOS) ON THE HEALTH OF PEOPLE LIVING NEARBY. THE
 2465 DIAGRAM ILLUSTRATES THE NUMBER OF RECORDS IDENTIFIED, SCREENED, ASSESSED FOR ELIGIBILITY,
 2466 EXCLUDED AND INCLUDED IN THE REVIEW.
 2467
 2468
 2469